

Deliverable D6.4 Project Handbook Final version and lessons learnt

Project Title (Grant agreement no.):	ELIXIR-CONVERGE: Connect and align ELIXIR Nodes to deliver sustainable FAIR life-science data management services (871075)		
Project Acronym (EC Call):	ELIXIR-CONVERGE (H2020-INFRADEV-2018-2020)		
WP No & Title:	WP6 Project Management and Scientific Coordination		
WP leader(s):	Juan Arenas Marquez (ELIXIR Hub)		
Deliverable Lead Beneficiary:	1 - ELIXIR Hub		
Contractual delivery date:	30/11/2022	Actual delivery date:	25/07/2023
Delayed:	Yes		
Partner(s) contributing to this deliverable:	EMBL (ELIXIR Hub)		
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Acknowledgments (not grant participants):			
Reviewers:	ELIXIR-CONVERGE Management Board (MB) members.		

Log of changes

DATE	Mvm	Who	Description
30/09/2022	0v1	Juan Arenas	Initial version
17/07/2023	0v2	Nikki Coutts (ELIXIR Hub)	Sent to PMU after incorporating internal WP feedback
17/07/2023	0v3	Nikki Coutts (ELIXIR Hub)	Circulated to the MB for final review before submission
25/07/2023	0v4	Juan Arenas (ELIXIR Hub), Nikki Coutts (ELIXIR Hub)	MB comments addressed
25/07/2023	1v0	Nikki Coutts (ELIXIR Hub)	Final version to be uploaded into EC Portal

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1. Executive Summary

This report provides an update to the second version of the ELIXIR-CONVERGE Project Handbook, shown in Deliverable D6.3¹.

The project handbook follows the Open PM² best practices to provide the board members and the project participants with a clear definition of their roles and responsibilities as well as the relevant processes and assets the project will use to ensure contractual commitments in the Grant Agreement are delivered on time and within the scope and budget and with the expected level of quality.

2. Contribution toward project objectives

The project handbook defines the project process that provides the framework to accomplish all projects objectives within the scope, budget and the required level of quality, therefore, we can say with confidence that this deliverable contributes to all objectives as listed below:

Objective no. / Key Result no. Description	Contributed to:
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¹ <https://zenodo.org/record/5146094>

Objective 1: Develop a sustainable and scalable operating model for transnational life-science data management support by leveraging national capabilities (WP1, WP5)	
Key Result 1.1: Established European expert network of data stewards that connect national data centres and similar infrastructures and drive the development of interoperable solutions following international best practice, including national interpretations of the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)	Yes
Key Result 1.2: Development of joint guidelines and common toolkit that are adopted into funder recommendations, with support available nationally and in local languages	Yes
Key Result 1.3: The catalogue of successful national business models incorporated into national strategies	Yes
Key Result 1.4: The developed “sustainable and scalable operating model for transnational life-science data management support” is adopted into national ELIXIR Node	Yes
Objective 2: Strengthen Europe’s data management capacity through a comprehensive training programme delivered throughout the European Research Area (WP2, WP6)	
Key Result 2.1: A comprehensive ELIXIR Training and Capacity building programme in Data Management, directed at both data managers and ELIXIR users, and connected to the national training programmes in Data Management in the ELIXIR Nodes and prospective ELIXIR Member countries.	Yes
Key Result 2.2: Development of a collective group of trainers that support scalable deployment of Data Management training across ELIXIR Nodes.	Yes
Key Result 2.3: A substantial cohort of data managers, Node coordinators and researchers with specific data management skills, business planning and knowledge of transnational operations across the ELIXIR Nodes	Yes
Objective 3: Align national data management standards and services through a sustainable, scalable and cost-effective data management toolkit (WP2, WP3, WP5)	
Key Result 3.1: Assemble a full-stack harmonised common toolkit comprising all aspects of data management: from data capture, annotation, and sharing; to integration with analysis platforms and making the data publicly available according to international standards.	Yes
Key Result 3.2: Provide exemplar toolkit configurations for prioritised demonstrators to serve as templates for future use.	Yes
Key Result 3.3: Establish national capacity in using as well as updating, extending and sustaining the toolkit across the ERA.	Yes

Key Result 3.4: Enable 'FAIR at source' practice for data generation, and analytical process pipeline implementation by flexible deployment of the toolkit in national operations	Yes
Objective 4: Align national investments to drive local impact and global influence of ELIXIR (WP4,WP6)	
Key Result 4.1: Development of a Node Impact Assessment Toolkit based on RI-PATHS methodology.	Yes
Key Result 4.2: Adoption of Impact assessment in ELIXIR Nodes, supported by Node coordinators network and feedback on applicability from dialogues with national funders.	Yes
Key Result 4.3: Creation of national public-private partnerships and industry outreach where open life-science data and services stimulate local bioeconomy	Yes
Key Result 4.4: Growth in reach, impact and engagement of stakeholder communication assessed by established ELIXIR Communications metrics	Yes
Key Result 4.5: Initiating and advancing discussions on Membership (EU and international) or strategic partnerships (international countries) following ELIXIR-CONVERGE workshops.	Yes

3. Introduction

The aim of this deliverable was to provide an update to the second version of the project handbook following the Open PM² best practices. It was defined that the handbook must provide the board members and the project participants with a clear definition of their roles and responsibilities as well as the relevant processes and assets that the project must use to ensure the contractual commitments as defined in the Grant Agreement are delivered; not only on time but within the scope and budget and with the expected level of quality.

The updated version of the Project Handbook (see Appendix 1) includes details of the new Partners and Work Packages added as part of an uplift to the project.

The live version is stored in the ELIXIR-CONVERGE Google Drive, which all project participants have access to.

4. Description of work accomplished

The description of work accomplished and results have been outlined below.

The finalised Project Handbook 3v0, up to date as of 17 July 2023, can be viewed in Appendix 1.

The live and evolving Project Handbook can be accessed in Appendix 2.

In Figure 4.1 (below) you can see the Table of Contents used in the Project Handbook which is adapted from the Open PM² template² using the prior project handbook preparation experience of the Project Management Team. The PM² Methodology originated from the European Commission and Open PM² provides many guidelines and templates to facilitate the management and documentation of EC projects.

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[https://webgate.ec.europa.eu/fpfis/wikis/display/openPM2/Artefacts?preview=/175357231/351800464/\(OPM2-04.P.TPL.v3.0\).Project_Handbook.\(ProjectName\).\(dd-mm-yyyy\).\(vx.x\).docx](https://webgate.ec.europa.eu/fpfis/wikis/display/openPM2/Artefacts?preview=/175357231/351800464/(OPM2-04.P.TPL.v3.0).Project_Handbook.(ProjectName).(dd-mm-yyyy).(vx.x).docx)

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Figure 4.1 ELIXIR-CONVERGE Project Handbook - Table of Contents

4.1 Update of processes as defined in the Project Handbook

All project participants are welcome, and actively encouraged, to suggest updates to the processes which were defined in the Project Handbook. The Project Handbook is designed to be a living, adaptable resource and therefore, as new processes have been refined and defined, the Project Handbook has and must be updated to avoid becoming stagnant and of no help to project partners. This deliverable contains the final formal update.

5. Conclusions

The project handbook provides the framework for the management of the ELIXIR-CONVERGE project. The Project Management Team have monitored the relevance of the handbook regularly during the duration of the project and adapted it as required to ensure that it remains relevant, meets the needs of the project participants and fulfils the objectives of the deliverable.

6. Impact

The project handbook and the associated project assets (e.g. the project monitoring tool) provides the framework for the monitoring and delivery of the tasks and objectives of each of the nine work packages at both the technical and financial level.

The project monitoring tool, designed and implemented for the ELIXIR-CONVERGE project has already proved useful to the project partners and BioData, the Portuguese distributed e-infrastructure for biological data and the Portuguese ELIXIR Node, have requested adopting the format for the monitoring of their own internal projects.

7. Next Steps

The project handbook is kept as a live document, available for review and modification at any point during the project duration to ensure it remains a valuable project resource. Project participants have easy access to the document at all times from the project Google Drive and are recommended to rely on it as a first point of contact when they have project management related questions.

8. Deviation from Description of Action

Following the mid-term review meeting the consortium agreed on a number of changes to be introduced in line with the Description of Action (DoA) and in order to maximise the outputs and impact of the project. Of the request listed below, four of them (1,9,10 and 17) were incorporated into

the in the third amendment while the others will be incorporated in the final technical report (following advice received) as they only require transfer of resources between beneficiaries.

<p>Request 1: Partial takeover of rights and obligations: DTL-P to HealthRI</p> <p><u>Justification:</u> DTL-P is still existing despite most staff (all staff related to H2020 ELIXIR projects) being transferred to Health-RI - PTRO is therefore required (set up Health-RI as new beneficiary)</p> <p><u>Implementation:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Health-RI to join as a new beneficiary from 1/1/2023 • Health-RI to take over DTL Rights and obligations from 1/1/2023 <p><u>Sections Affected:</u> Part A & Part B</p>																																																																															
<p>Request 2: Production of material/training to promote the adoption of Best Practices on Data Management coming out of ELIXIR-CONVERGE (WP1)</p> <p><u>Justification:</u> Increasing the adoption of Best Practices in data management will contribute to increasing the European capacity on Data Management, growing the data management community and therefore contributing to ensuring the LTS of the project outputs.</p> <p><u>Implementation:</u> Increase of project total budget to €105,815 (No changes on EC contribution) as follows:</p> <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Beneficiary</th> <th>PM</th> <th>PC</th> <th>ODC</th> <th>SC</th> <th>IC</th> <th>TC</th> <th>Comments</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>HRI</td> <td>2.00</td> <td>€19,533</td> <td></td> <td></td> <td>€4,883</td> <td>€24,417</td> <td>Request 2 - WP1 Best practices developer</td> </tr> <tr> <td>HITS</td> <td>1.00</td> <td>€5,050</td> <td></td> <td></td> <td>€1,263</td> <td>€6,313</td> <td>Request 2 - WP1 Best practices developer</td> </tr> <tr> <td>INESC-ID</td> <td>1.00</td> <td>€7,601</td> <td></td> <td></td> <td>€1,900</td> <td>€9,501</td> <td>Request 2 - WP1 Best practices developer</td> </tr> <tr> <td>UCAM</td> <td>1.00</td> <td>€7,018</td> <td></td> <td></td> <td>€1,755</td> <td>€8,773</td> <td>Request 2 - WP1 Best practices developer</td> </tr> <tr> <td>UiO</td> <td>1.00</td> <td>€7,703</td> <td></td> <td></td> <td>€1,926</td> <td>€9,629</td> <td>Request 2 - WP1 Best practices developer</td> </tr> <tr> <td>UNIPD</td> <td>2.00</td> <td>€13,027</td> <td></td> <td></td> <td>€3,257</td> <td>€16,284</td> <td>Request 2 - WP1 Best practices developer</td> </tr> <tr> <td>UOCHB</td> <td>2.00</td> <td>€10,920</td> <td></td> <td></td> <td>€2,730</td> <td>€13,650</td> <td>Request 2 - WP1 Best practices developer</td> </tr> <tr> <td>UU</td> <td>2.00</td> <td>€13,800</td> <td></td> <td></td> <td>€3,450</td> <td>€17,250</td> <td>Request 2 - WP1 Best practices developer</td> </tr> </tbody> </table> <p>³</p> <p><u>Note:</u> ELIXIR/EMBL-EBI maximum EC contribution requested will be reduced by the same amount to avoid increasing the EC contribution.</p> <p><u>Sections Affected:</u> Part A</p>								Beneficiary	PM	PC	ODC	SC	IC	TC	Comments	HRI	2.00	€19,533			€4,883	€24,417	Request 2 - WP1 Best practices developer	HITS	1.00	€5,050			€1,263	€6,313	Request 2 - WP1 Best practices developer	INESC-ID	1.00	€7,601			€1,900	€9,501	Request 2 - WP1 Best practices developer	UCAM	1.00	€7,018			€1,755	€8,773	Request 2 - WP1 Best practices developer	UiO	1.00	€7,703			€1,926	€9,629	Request 2 - WP1 Best practices developer	UNIPD	2.00	€13,027			€3,257	€16,284	Request 2 - WP1 Best practices developer	UOCHB	2.00	€10,920			€2,730	€13,650	Request 2 - WP1 Best practices developer	UU	2.00	€13,800			€3,450	€17,250	Request 2 - WP1 Best practices developer
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<p>Request 3: <u>Establishment of a Community of Practice in Data Management and Stewardship (WP2)</u></p> <p><u>Justification:</u> Work towards the establishment of a new ELIXIR community (CoP) that could</p>																																																																															

³ PM: Person Months, PC: Personnel Costs, ODC: Other Direct Costs, SC: Subcontracting, IC: Indirect Costs, TC: Total Costs

then be supported by ELIXIR funding received from MS building on the successful roll-out of such a community in the UK by members of ELIXIR UK.

Implementation: Increase of project total budget to €72,392 (No changes on EC contribution) as follows :

Beneficiary	PM	PC	ODC	SC	IC	TC	Comments
HITS			€16,284		€4,071	€20,355	Request 3 - Datastewarship WP2
UiO	3.00	€18,487			€4,622	€23,109	Request 3 - Datastewarship WP2
UNIMAN			€23,142		€5,786	€28,928	Request 3 - Datastewarship WP2

Note: ELIXIR/EMBL-EBI maximum EC contribution requested will be reduced by the same amount to avoid increasing the EC contribution.

As agreed within WP2, we will build on the experience and knowledge of the ELIXIR UK Node to establish a successful CoP at the UK level. To that end contract will be established between the ELIXIR Hub and the institutions involved in the rollout of the ELIXIR UK CoP as follows by reallocating ELIXIR/EMBL-EBI ODC budget to subcontracting as follows:

Beneficiary	PM	PC	ODC	SC	IC	TC	Comments
ELIXIR/EMBL-EBI			-€6,782	€8,478	-€1,696	€0	Contract with the University Bradford to provide expertise on establishing the Data Stewardship CoP
ELIXIR/EMBL-EBI			-€3,680	€4,600	-€920	€0	Contract with the University Bradford to support CoP event
ELIXIR/EMBL-EBI			-€5,441	€6,802	-€1,360	-€0	Contract with the University Cardiff to provide expertise on establishing the Data Stewardship CoP

Sections Affected: Part A & Part B

Request 4: Strengthen mid-management capabilities across ELIXIR Node /members: ELITMA (WP2/WP6)

Justification: ESFRI recommendation for the LTS of RIs highlight the need to develop professional managers to such end ELITMA will deliver a set of practical training modules to increase management capacity across ELIXIR nodes in a number of topics not limited to Governance, Strategic Management, Financial Sustainability, Project Management, Communications

Implementation: Increase of project total budget in €111,781 (No changes on EC contribution) as follows:

Beneficiary	PM	PC	ODC	SC	IC	TC	Comments
CSC			€20,000		€5,000	€25,000	Request 4. - ELITMA
HRI	2.50	€24,417			€6,104	€30,521	Request 4. - ELITMA
INESC-ID	5.00	€38,003			€9,501	€47,503	Request 4. - ELITMA

Note: ELIXIR/EMBL-EBI maximum EC contribution requested will be reduced on the same amount to avoid increasing the EC contribution.

Sections Affected: Part A

Request 5: RDMKit, communications and scaling up: consolidation review and evolution of the RDMKit as a platform to scale up data management practices across disciplines and domains(WP3).

Justification: Expand the use of RDMKit on a daily basis by researchers across disciplines and domains, expanding the community of users and contributors, which will increase the LTS.

Implementation: Increase of project total budget to €134,739 (No changes on EC contribution) as follows:

Beneficiary	PM	PC	ODC	SC	IC	TC	Comments
BSC	0.33	€1,981			€495	€2,477	Request 5 - RDMKit
HRI	1.33	€13,022			€3,255	€16,277	Request 5 - RDMKit
HITS	0.33	€1,703			€426	€2,129	Request 5 - RDMKit
INESC-ID	0.33	€2,533			€633	€3,167	Request 5 - RDMKit
UIB	1.33	€10,270			€2,568	€12,838	Request 5 - RDMKit
UiO	0.33	€2,567	€7,000		€2,392	€11,959	Request 5 - RDMKit
UNILU	0.33	€2,565			€641	€3,206	Request 5 - RDMKit
UNIMAN	2.33	€20,892			€5,223	€26,115	Request 5 - RDMKit
UOCHB	3.00	€16,380			€4,095	€20,475	Request 5 - RDMKit
UU	1.33	€9,200			€2,300	€11,500	Request 5 - RDMKit
VIB	2.33	€19,677			€4,919	€24,596	Request 5 - RDMKit

Note: ELIXIR/EMBL-EBI maximum EC contribution requested will be reduced by the same amount to avoid increasing the EC contribution.

Sections Affected: Part A

Request 6:Accelerate FEAGA deployment: Support deployment of FEAGA in the second round of countries (WP7)

Justification: Deployment of additional FEAGA nodes increasing the technical capacity and the participation of countries in the federation ensuring LTS

Implementation: Increase of project total budget in €123,749 (No changes on EC contribution) as follows:

Beneficiary	PM	PC	ODC	SC	IC	TC	Comments
ATHENA-RIC	0.50	€2,000	€1,000		€750	€3,750	Request 6 - FEGA Node expansion
BSC	1.68	€9,998	€2,000		€3,000	€14,998	Request 6 - FEGA Node expansion
BSRC	2.00	€8,000	€1,000		€2,250	€11,250	Request 6 - FEGA Node expansion
CRG	1.68	€10,001	€4,000		€3,500	€17,501	Request 6 - FEGA Node expansion
CSC	1.63	€10,001	€2,000		€3,000	€15,001	Request 6 - FEGA Node expansion
ELIXIR/EMBL-EBI	1.29	€10,002	€4,000		€3,501	€17,503	Request 6 - FEGA Node expansion
INESC-ID	1.32	€9,998	€1,000		€2,750	€13,748	Request 6 - FEGA Node expansion
SIB	0.78	€10,000	€2,000		€3,000	€15,000	Request 6 - FEGA Node expansion
UIB	0.65	€4,999	€1,000		€1,500	€7,499	Request 6 - FEGA Node expansion
UiO	0.65	€4,999	€1,000		€1,500	€7,499	Request 6 - FEGA Node expansion

Note: ELIXIR/EMBL-EBI maximum EC contribution requested will be reduced by the same amount to avoid increasing the EC contribution.

Sections Affected: Part A

Request 7: Strength of WP9 Leadership

Justification: Isabel Cuesta (ISCI3) will act as WP9 Leader to cover Aitana Neves (SIB) maternity leave to enable the smooth operations of WP9 until the end of the project. To fund the additional effort, ISCI3 will have to deploy resources that would be transferred from the ELIXIR Hub budget to ISCI3

Implementation: increase of project total budget in €43,830 (No changes on EC contribution) as follows:

Beneficiary	PM	PC	ODC	SC	IC	TC	Comments
ISCI3	8.00	€35,064			€8,766	€43,830	Increase ISCI3 resources to takeover WP9 leadership to cover maternity leave

Note: ELIXIR/EMBL-EBI maximum EC contribution requested will be reduced by the same amount to avoid increasing the EC contribution.

Sections Affected: Part A & Part B

Request 8: Transfers of resources from UU to UNIPD for the organisation of WP2 events and related activities

Justification: Organisation of WP2 events and related activities

Implementation: Transfers of resources from UU to Unipd as follows.

Beneficiary	PM	PC	ODC	SC	IC	TC	Comments
UNIPD	2.00	€8,974	€2,446		€2,855	€14,276	Transfers of resources from UU to UNIPD for the organisation of WP2 events and related activities
UU			-€11,421		-€2,855	-€14,276	Transfers of resources from UU to UNIPD for the organisation of WP2 events and related activities

Sections Affected: Part A

Request 9: Correction of the description of the kind contribution for Third parties associated with BSC

Justification: the current text does not reflect that In-kind contribution is provided on the Third Parties' premises. Neutral change no changes in budget distribution or EC contribution.

Implementation: amend text on Part B.

Sections affected: Part B

Request 10: TTK - Remove UD as Third Party

Justification: Tasks to be covered by TTK.

Implementation: Remove UD entry from Part B.

Sections affected: Part B

Request 11: TTK correction of a mistake in the number of PM introduced in the last amendment

Justification: TTK should have 5PM in WP1, UP should have 0PM - currently TTK 1PM, UP 4PM)

Implementation: Update PMs in part A for TTK and UP

Sections affected: Part A

Request 12: MU - Change to number of PMs

Justification: Due to the difference of the seniority of the staff finally participating in the project, we request to update the number of PMs in each WPs as described in the implementation section

Implementation:

- WP1: 4 PMs =>5,4 PM
- WP3: 1 PM =>1,6 PM

Sections affected: Part A

Request 13: CNR - Change to number of PMs

Justification: Due to the difference of the seniority of the staff finally participating in the project, we request to update the number of PMs in each WPs as described in the implementation section

Implementation:

We are currently forecasting the utilisation of 23.26 PM instead of the 11.5 PM initially estimated as follows:

- WP2: 4 PM => 5.93 PM
- WP4: 1.5 PM => 3.90 PM
- WP9: 6 PM => 13.43 PM

Sections affected: Part A

Request 14: UCAM - Change to a number of PMs

Justification: Due to a change in staff member carrying out the work we need to increase the number of PMs slightly.

Implementation: Increase WP2 by 4 extra PMs (no change in the budget)

WP2: 6 PMs => 10 PMs

Sections affected: Part A

Request 15: Reallocation of funding for the SME event organisation in Switzerland

Justification: Transfer of funding for the organisation of SME event in Switzerland from ELIXIR/EMBL-EBI ODC budget to SIB.

Implementation:

Beneficiary	PM	PC	ODC	SC	IC	TC	Comments
ELIXIR/EMBL-EBI			-€19,750		-€4,938	-€24,688	Transfer of funds from ELIXIR/EMBL-EBI to SIB for SME event 2021
SIB			€19,750		€4,938	€24,688	Transfer of funds from ELIXIR/EMBL-EBI to SIB for SME event 2021

Sections affected: Part A

Request 16: DTU transfer of remaining budget to UCPH as PI has moved from DTU to UCPH

Justification: UCPH will take over remaining activities previously assigned to DTU, after Søren Brunak has moved from DTU to UCPH

Implementation:

Remaining budget after MTR (€171,727.92) to be transferred to UCPH. UCPH will replace DTU in the remaining activities with the remaining effort.

Sections Affected: Part A & Part B

Request 17: SIB - transfer of funds to sub-contracting (for training video production)

Justification: In the scope of ELIXIR-CONVERGE WP2 / Task 2.4 we would like to create a short video to raise awareness of PIs about data management good practices.

Currently, this project involves 12 people from 10 ELIXIR Nodes. This group agreed that a short video would be the most adapted format for this audience (PIs) and at the same time to spread good practices through new ELIXIR Members and Communities. To implement this video professionally

Implementation: Reallocation of €12,000 from SIB ODC to Subcontracting

Beneficiary	PM	PC	ODC	SC	IC	TC	Comments
SIB			-€9,600	€12,000	-€2,400		Subcontracting of video training production SIB

Sections Affected: Part A

Appendix 1: ELIXIR-CONVERGE Project Handbook 2v0

The project handbook copied here is a snapshot of the updated version as of 17th July 2023. As the project handbook is a live, and evolving document the latest version can be found linked to from Appendix 2, below.

871075 - ELIXIR-CONVERGE

Project Handbook

Date: July 2023

Version: 3v0

Document Control Information

Settings	Value
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Project Title:	ELIXIR-CONVERGE
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DOCUMENT HISTORY

The Document Author is authorised to make the following types of changes to the document without requiring that the document be re-approved:

- Editorial, formatting, and spelling
- Clarification

To request a change to this document, contact the Document Author or Owner. Changes to this document are summarised in the following table.

Revision	Date	Created by	Short Description of Changes
Vo.1	15/04/20	Hannah Hurst & Nikki Coutts	First draft of full handbook structure
Vo.2	27/04/20	Juan Arenas & Hannah Hurst	Review of draft and closed comments and circulated to MB for review
Vo.3	20/05/20	Hannah Hurst	Final comments closed
V1.0	26/05/20	Hannah Hurst	Finalised to submit as a deliverable
V1.1	16/07/2021	Nikki Coutts	Review/update of handbook
V1.2	21/07/2021	Juan Arenas & Nikki Coutts	Review of draft and closed comments and circulated to MB for review
V1.3	29/07/2021	Nikki Coutts	Final comments closed
V2.0	29/07/2021	Nikki Coutts	Finalised to submit as a deliverable
V2.1	14/07/2023	Nikki Coutts	Review/update of handbook
V2.2	17/07/2023	Juan Arenas & Nikki Coutts	Review of draft and closed comments and circulated to MB for review
V2.3	24/07/2023	Nikki Coutts	Final comments closed
V3.0	24/07/2023	Nikki Coutts	Finalised to submit as a deliverable

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1. ABOUT THE PROJECT HANDBOOK

The Project Handbook provides a complete overview of the management and administrative procedures and principles to ensure an efficient execution of the ELIXIR-CONVERGE project, thus contributing to the production of high quality project results. The Project Handbook documents the selected approach for implementing the project goals, including the milestones and deliverables and relevant KPIs. It also highlights the key controlling processes to be used, the project policies and rules, and the overall management approach, including, but not limited to management structure, tasks, decision-making procedures, responsibilities and roles.

The Project Handbook is an important document since it contains all relevant planning information that the consortium partners will use as a framework for delivery during the course of the project.

The Project Handbook becomes the basis for managing the project throughout its lifecycle and is an important point of reference for all consortium partners and stakeholders. The Project Handbook is kept up to date throughout the life of the project through annual updates.

Language adopted throughout the documents aims to be clear and concise.

Please note that this Project Handbook is circulated as a guidance document only. It should not be relied upon for making any legal assessments, for which Beneficiaries should always refer to the Grant Agreement (including its annexes)⁴ and the Consortium Agreement⁵.

2. PROJECT OVERVIEW

2.1. Basic Project Information

⁴ https://drive.google.com/open?id=1hyHR5399GOWNDi3EsDOLCr_TEohCRXwp

⁵ As of 16th July the amended Consortium Agreement is being signed by partners

Project Call:

INFRADEV-03-2018-2019 - Individual support to ESFRI and other world-class research infrastructures

Project Title: Connect and align ELIXIR Nodes to deliver sustainable FAIR life-science data management services

Project Acronym: ELIXIR-CONVERGE

Grant Agreement N°: 871075

Call topic: H2020-INFRADEV-2019-2

Project start date: 1st February 2020

Project end date: 31st July 2023

Duration: 42 months

Project budget: €9,800,000

Number of beneficiaries: 44

Number of LTPs: 15

2.2. Short Names of the Consortium Partners

Table 1. Beneficiaries

Beneficiary n°	Name of the consortium partner	Short name
1 (Coordinator)	EUROPEAN MOLECULAR BIOLOGY LABORATORY (FOR ELIXIR AND EMBL-EBI)	ELIXIR / EMBL-EBI
2	VIB	VIB
3	SIB INSTITUT SUISSE DE BIOINFORMATIQUE	SIB
4	UNIVERSITY OF CYPRUS	UCY
5	THE CYPRUS FOUNDATION FOR MUSCULAR DYSTROPHY RESEARCH (CYPRUS SCHOOL OF MOLECULAR MEDICINE)	CING
6	USTAV ORGANICKE CHEMIE A BIOCHEMIE, AV CR, V.V.I.	UOCHB
7	HEIDELBERG INSTITUTE FOR THEORETICAL STUDIES	HITS
8	DANMARKS TEKNISKE UNIVERSITET	DTU
9	TARTU ULIKOOL	UT
10	BARCELONA SUPERCOMPUTING CENTER	BSC
11	CSC-TIETEEN TIETOTEKNIKAN KESKUS OY	CSC
12	L'INSTITUT NATIONAL DE RECHERCHE EN AGRICULTURE, ALIMENTATION ET ENVIRONNEMENT	INRAE
13	CENTRE NATIONAL DE LA RECHERCHE SCIENTIFIQUE	CNRS
14	BIOMEDICAL SCIENCES RESEARCH CENTER ALEXANDER FLEMING	BSRC

15	ATHENA RESEARCH AND INNOVATION CENTER IN INFORMATION, COMMUNICATION AND KNOWLEDGE TECHNOLOGIES	ATHENA-RIC
16	CENTRE FOR RESEARCH AND TECHNOLOGY HELLAS	CERTH
17	MAGYAR TUDOMANYOS AKADEMIA TERMESZETTUDOMANYI KUTATOKOZPONT	TTK
18	UNIVERSITY COLLEGE DUBLIN, NATIONAL UNIVERSITY OF IRELAND, DUBLIN	UCD
19	WEIZMANN INSTITUTE OF SCIENCE	WEIZMANN
20	CONSIGLIO NAZIONALE DELLE RICERCHE	CNR
21	UNIVERSITE DU LUXEMBOURG	UNILU
22	STICHTING DTL PROJECTS	DTL-Projects
23	UNIVERSITETET I BERGEN	UIB
24	INESC ID - INSTITUTO DE ENGENHARIA DE SISTEMAS E COMPUTADORES, INVESTIGACAO E DESENVOLVIMENTO EM LISBOA	INESC-ID
25	FUNDAÇÃO CALOUSTE GULBENKIAN -INSTITUTO GULBENKIAN DE CIÊNCIA	IGC
26	UPPSALA UNIVERSITET	UU
27	UNIVERZA V LJUBLJANI	UL
28	THE UNIVERSITY OF MANCHESTER	UNIMAN
29	THE CHANCELLOR MASTERS AND SCHOLARS OF THE UNIVERSITY OF CAMBRIDGE	UCAM
30	THE CENTRE FOR GENOMIC REGULATION	CRG
31	UNIVERSITY OF PECS	UP
32	UNIVERSITY OF CAPE TOWN	UCT
33	UNIVERSITY OF KWAZULU-NATAL	UKZN
34	ALBERT-LUDWIGS-UNIVERSITAET FREIBURG	ALU-FR
35	DEUTSCHES KREBSFORSCHUNGSZENTRUM HEIDELBERG	DKFZ
36	EBERHARD KARLS UNIVERSITAET TUEBINGEN	EKUT
37	FUNDACION PUBLICA ANDALUZA PROGRESO Y SALUD M.P.	FPS
38	INSTITUTO DE SALUD CARLOS III	ISCI

39	AGENCIA ESTATAL CONSEJO SUPERIOR DE INVESTIGACIONES CIENTIFICAS	CSIC
40	INSTYTUT CHEMII BIOORGANICZNEJ POLSKIEJ AKADEMII NAUK	IBCH
41	THE CHANCELLOR, MASTERS AND SCHOLARS OF THE UNIVERSITY OF OXFORD	UOXF
42	KOBENHAVNS UNIVERSITET	UCPH
43	GESUNDHEIT OSTERREICH GMBH	GOG
44	STICHTING HEALTH-RI	HRI

2.3. Project Acronyms

Table 2. Project Acronyms

Abbreviation	Meaning
CA	Consortium Agreement - Agreement concluded amongst ELIXIR-CONVERGE beneficiaries for the implementation of the Grant Agreement. Such an agreement shall not affect the parties' obligations to the Community and/or to one another arising from the Grant Agreement.
CDA	Confidential Disclosure Agreement
Consortium	The ELIXIR-CONVERGE Consortium, comprising the named legal entities.
DMP	Data Management Plan
DoA	Description of Action
EAB	Ethics Advisory Board
EC	European Commission
GA	Grant Agreement - The agreement signed between the beneficiaries and the EC for the undertaking of the ELIXIR-CONVERGE project
HoN	Heads of Nodes
IAC	Industry Advisory Committee
IC	Indirect Costs
KPI	Key Performance Indicator

MoU	Memorandum of Understanding
ODC	Other direct costs
PM	Project Manager
PMs	Person months
PMT	Project Management Team
Project	The sum of all activities carried out in the framework of the Grant Agreement.
QA	Quality Assurance
SAB	Scientific Advisory Board
WP	Work Package
WPL	Work Package Leader

2.4. Project Summary

The diversity, complexity and volume, as well as privacy and regulatory considerations, necessitate a collaborative and federated approach to life-science data. For scientists to find and share data across Europe and world-wide, ELIXIR needs to continuously develop and connect its services. The international ecosystem provided by ELIXIR – with 220 institutes in 23 Nodes, connecting hundreds of bioinformatics services – is globally unique and a competitive advantage for European research. Through our national Nodes ELIXIR has the geographical spread, service portfolio and expertise to fulfil our ambition that every European project uses FAIR data based on common standards, tools and services.

The initial operational phase of ELIXIR, supported by the H2020 ELIXIR-EXCELERATE project, focussed on the coordination and delivery of bioinformatics services from national Nodes. This lay the foundation for a coordinated European infrastructure. ELIXIR-CONVERGE will build on these achievements to deliver another critical component: the provisioning, across Europe, of distributed local support for data management based on a toolkit for researchers that enables lifecycle management for their research data according to international standards.

ELIXIR-CONVERGE will develop the national operations of such a distributed research infrastructure to drive good data management, reproducibility and reuse in a heterogeneous funding landscape. Over 42 months and with partners from our 22 Nodes, ELIXIR-CONVERGE takes the next step to realise a European data federation where interconnected national operations, strategically managed via national research infrastructure roadmaps, allow users to extract knowledge from life science’s large, diverse and distributed datasets. By connecting ELIXIR Nodes to provide FAIR data management as a service, ELIXIR-CONVERGE will build

national capacity and create a blueprint for operating sustainable Nodes in distributed research infrastructures.

ELIXIR-CONVERGE is designed to deliver the major, complex and outstanding issues of building and harmonising national data management practices, access to human capital, impact assessments and national roadmap positioning. ELIXIR-CONVERGE will harmonise toolkits, operations and monitoring indicators.

Specifically we aim to achieve this sustained national capacity for life science research data management by delivering results against four project objectives:

- Objective 1: Develop a sustainable and scalable operating model for transnational life-science data management support by leveraging national capabilities
- Objective 2: Strengthen Europe's data management capacity through a comprehensive training programme delivered throughout the European Research Area
- Objective 3: Align national data management standards and services through a sustainable, scalable and cost-effective data management toolkit
- Objective 4: Align national investments to drive local impact and global influence of ELIXIR

Due to the provision of emergency funding from the EC as a result of the COVID-19 pandemic, the scope of work of the project has been extended, with three further Work Packages added. These are working on the following:

- collating the national COVID-19 DMPs and metadata requirements. The results will be used as part of the impact assessment and long-term sustainability strategy (WP₄) to demonstrate the added value for pan-European COVID-19 data management collaboration.
- Building on the competence in ELIXIR-CONVERGE (WP₁, WP₃ and WP₄) to facilitate the development of the Federated EGA node maturity model by examining how this model aligns with the national or regional plans for COVID-19 host data sharing initiatives.
- Provision of the technical and operational components of the European COVID-19 Data Platform. These components will serve to strengthen national operations around COVID-19 data - on both viral and human data sides - through the ELIXIR Nodes.
- Assembly of existing elements of informatics infrastructure, from core EMBL-EBI infrastructure and pathogen-focused tools built under the COMPARE project, extension and enhancement of these elements and their operationalisation in both the COVID-19 Data Portal and SARS-CoV-2 Data Hubs.
- Mobilisation of viral genomes from national sequencing efforts in Europe and beyond into truly open data resources for surveillance of COVID-19 variants and exposing variation data rapidly for analysis. This will be achieved by linking nascent and established national sequencing efforts to the COVID-19 Data Platform by setting up submission and annotation pipelines to the European Nucleotide Archive (ENA). Participating efforts will commit to open sharing of variant data through ENA.

2.5. Project Scope and Work Structure

The strategy underpinning this project is straightforward: the project aims to leverage *“fostering international cooperation to support the global dimension of data management and interoperability among RIs generating data “products” software and services for science and society”* as a driver to further develop *“adequate framework conditions for effective governance and sustainable long-term funding for RI”* at the national Nodes and European Hub. In particular we aim to develop better alignment of national roadmaps and investment in life-science data and ensure that the national-level investments across ELIXIR Nodes are fully synchronised with country investments into the Europe-wide ELIXIR Programme.

A key consideration is that ELIXIR Nodes operate within the context of national research infrastructures, national research data policies and are not only dealing with data produced by RIs but also by many other different types of projects: national, European and global. The national research environments are, and should be, diverse and reflect the strengths and priorities of individual countries. Data management policies also diverge and are managed differently across countries.

Responding to these drivers, this project is designed to provide a range of tools such as scientific best practice (WP1), cataloguing and comparing business models (WP1), development of a shared data management toolkit that can be adapted to local needs (WP3) and a Node Impact Assessment Toolkit (WP4) that together within investments in training and capacity building (WP2) allows ELIXIR Nodes to prioritise and implement those aspects that best strengthen the national operations. We note that the importance of responding to national priorities and different environments has also been recognised in the ESFRI recommendations: *“Research Infrastructures should take full advantage of RI self-organisation and coordination at the EU level, which allows efficient sharing of best practices among them and includes also mutual learning exercises”* In addition, collaborative benchmarking, standardisation, sharing and development of good practices provides excellent opportunities for individual development and, in the words of ESFRI, *“develop and encourage some of the rather unusual career tracks on which RIs rely”*.

Figure 1. ELIXIR-CONVERGE is organised around an expert network (WP1) that connects Node data management programmes. During the project, this expert network will develop an operational model (including access and cost recovery models) that allows international collaborations to draw on harmonised and connected services from multiple national Nodes.

Table 3. Work Package Titles

Work package #	Title
WP1	Expert network
WP2	Training and Capacity Building
WP3	Common Data Management Toolkit
WP4	Communications, Industry, International, Impact and Sustainability
WP5	Demonstrator Projects
WP6	Project Management and Scientific Coordination
WP7	Federated European Genome-phenome Archives for transnational access of COVID-19 host data
WP8	European COVID-19 Data Portals
WP9	Mobilisation of SARS-CoV-2 variant surveillance data tracking services and tools

Following the mid term review meeting and taking into consideration the feedback received, the consortium agreed to engage in the activities below that are supported via the changes included in the deviation section of D6.4.

- WP1:
 - Production of materials/training to promote the adoption of Best Practices on Data Management coming out of ELIXIR-CONVERGE. This will contribute to increasing the European capacity on Data Management, growing the data management community and therefore contributing to ensuring the LTS of the project outputs.
- WP2:
 - Establishment of a new ELIXIR community, the 'Community of Practice' (CoP) in Data Management and Stewardship, which could then be supported by ELIXIR funding received from MS, building on the successful roll-out of such a community in the UK by members of ELIXIR UK.
- WP2 / WP6:
 - Strengthening of mid-management capabilities across ELIXIR Node /members. ESFRI have, for the LTS of RIs, highlighted the need to develop professional managers. To this end, ELITMA will deliver a set of practical training modules to increase management capacity across ELIXIR nodes in a number of topics not limited to Governance, Strategic Management, Financial Sustainability, Project Management and Communications.
- WP3:
 - A consolidation review, and evolution of the RDMKit as a platform, will be performed, in order to scale up data management practices across disciplines and domains. This will expand the community of users and contributors, which will increase the LTS.
- WP7:
 - The deployment of FEAGA in the second round of countries will be supported. This deployment of additional FEAGA nodes will increase the technical capacity and the participation of countries in the federation, ensuring LTS.

2.6. Project Coordination and Management

Work Package 6 (Project Management and Scientific Coordination) will establish effective project governance and internal communication procedures to allow for the flow of information within the project. It will also fulfil the administrative tasks associated with management of the project.

The overall goal of this WP is to oversee the project execution ensuring an effective and efficient coordination across all activities and participants to deliver the project goals, benefits and expected impact within time, scope and budget. In addition, we aim to build management capacity across ELIXIR to address specific ESFRI working group recommendations.

The Work Package sets out 4 clear objectives:

- 1) Establishment of the project governance structure mobilising the project resources and developing the project guidance
- 2) Efficient and effective project monitoring collecting KPIs and tracking risk and opportunities to assist the project boards on taking informed decisions at all levels
- 3) Develop and update the project data management plan along the project lifecycle
- 4) Build capacity in management to address ESFRI working group recommendations.

All tasks will contribute to the incremental version of the project handbook that will define and update the different plans and processes, including the monitoring of project metrics and lessons learned, which will contribute to the continuous improvement of EC funded projects.

3. PROJECT APPROACH

3.1. Required Project Documentation

Table 4. Required Project Documentations

Artefact	Yes/No	Location	If No, briefly explain the reason
Description of Action - Part A	✓	https://drive.google.com/open?id=1B8TPadY56WlQY_qrysnLvceKcqnllaJO	
Description of Action - Part B	✓	https://drive.google.com/open?id=1K66wz0jDS3K6VypdzyV67P9AlMPpKduW	
Grant Agreement	✓	https://drive.google.com/open?id=1gLhclTzFumCGuobTsZBPcZKFcPB2m5Qn	
Consortium Agreement - fully executed	✓		
Project Handbook (this document)	✓	https://docs.google.com/document/d/1Na1N_oAz1cFVks2c_ZY-8gFdxhmG-SnV2agoEdEABs/edit	
Project Master File	✓	https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1B_sK9Q8uwAQEOGY-PRBG08HbMgSrIKGE-MCrArKdXWo/edit#gid=0	
Data Management Plan	✓		
Other...			

3.2. Internal Conflict Resolution and Escalation

Conflicts are situations in which one or both parties perceive a threat. They are considered to be critical issues and can be raised by any of the project stakeholders. The Project Management Team should proactively identify, log and raise such issues for resolution.

In the event that an internal conflict arises at a given time, the project coordination and the management structure is formulated to support a bottom-up approach with respect to its resolution.

- Conflicts amongst Beneficiaries in any given activity will be discussed at the Work Package (WP) level with the help of the respective Work Package Leaders (WPLs).
- If unresolved, the issue will escalate to the Managing Board (MB), which, with the help of the PMT will use mediation to objectively aim to solve the issue.
- If unresolved and when the issue is significant enough, the Managing Board could then make a proposal to the Heads of Nodes Committee (HoN) to amicably resolve the issue. In case no solution can be found which is acceptable to the Beneficiaries involved in the dispute, the dispute resolution mechanisms of the Consortium Agreement will apply.

At all stages, beneficiaries can reach out to the PMT in case they feel a request has not been adequately dealt with.

4. PROJECT PROCESSES

4.1. Risk Management

4.1.1. Risk Identification and categorization

An initial list of key project risks has been identified during the preparation of the Action and a respective table of identified risks can be found in 1.3.5 of the DoA - Part A (Table 3.2b)⁶.

All beneficiaries are asked to screen their activities with regards to additional new risks and to promptly notify the PMT of any significant new risk(s) having the potential to affect the completion of the assigned WP.

4.1.2. Risk Assessment, registry and action plan

The PMT will add any new risks, including a description of the possible impact, to the risk table and bring any additional risk(s) to the attention of the MB who will discuss categorization and prioritisation.

⁶ Risks. P38: https://drive.google.com/open?id=1B8TPadY56WIOY_qrysnLvceKcqnlIaIQ

Prioritisation of the risks will be based on the possible impact (I) and the probability (II) of realisation of the risk. Based on the prioritisation appropriate mitigation activities and/or contingency plans will be developed.

An action plan for each identified risk has to be developed by the concerned work package and agreed by the MB as part of the risk management process. The list of identified risks are stored in the CONVERGE Google Drive, the agreed Document management system for the project. The risk log⁷ will be maintained and reviewed on a monthly basis during the Managing Board calls.

4.1.3. Risk monitoring

All identified risks and mitigation steps will be reviewed by the MB on a quarterly basis during their monthly TC. WPLs and Task leads are asked to actively contribute to this activity which will be overseen by the Project Coordinator and PMT.

An update of the risk assessment activity, including the major risks identified with their corresponding mitigation and contingency plans, will be included in the Periodic Reports to be annually submitted to the European Commission. This will include information on newly identified risks and risks which have been resolved.

WP6 will drive the risk management process, dealing with the identification, assessment and follow-up of threats and opportunities likely to affect the project performance as a whole.

For any questions related to project risks, contact converge-pm@elixir-europe.org.

4.2. Issue Management

The project issue management process defines the activities related to identifying, documenting, assessing, prioritising, assigning, resolving and controlling issues. It is a four step process that the Project Management Team (PMT) executes whenever required throughout the project lifecycle:

- **Issue Identification:** Issues can be identified by any project stakeholders throughout the project lifecycle, using different communication channels such as meetings and emails (converge-pm@elixir-europe.org). The issues are registered in the Issue Log.
- **Issue Assessment and Action Recommendation:** a first informal assessment by PMT, considers the category, impact, urgency and size of the issue, followed by a more detailed analysis to identify the root cause and recommend a solution. This information is documented in the Issue Log and used as input to the appropriate decision makers (based on the escalation process). The decision is documented in the Decision Log.
- **Actions Implementation:** After issues are evaluated and the remediation actions approved, the Project Management Team will incorporate these actions into the

⁷ Risk Log:

https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1B_sK9O8uwAQEOGY-PRBG08HbMgSrIKGE-MCrArKdXW0/edit#gid=1490449280

appropriate project related documentation such as the next amended Description of Action and logs.

- **Issue Control:** During the regular Project Management meetings the status of issues and related actions will be revised, and new issues identified. Additionally, PMT will report monthly the status of the major issues to the Managing Board and, when appropriate, to other project stakeholders.

For any questions related to project issues, contact:

converge-pm@elixir-europe.org.

4.3. Project Change Management

The project change management process defines the activities related to identifying, documenting, assessing, approving, prioritising, planning and controlling changes, and communicating them to all relevant stakeholders. It is a five step process that the Project Management Team (PMT) executes whenever required throughout the project lifecycle:

- **Change Identification:** a request for a change can be submitted formally via an email to PMT (converge-pm@elixir-europe.org), or can be identified and raised during meetings as a result of decisions, issues or risks. The requested change should then be captured in the Change Log⁸ including information to identify the change, such as the requestor, a short description, identification date, etc.
- **Change Assessment and Action Recommendation:** the size and impact of the change on the project scope, schedule, cost, quality, risk, and other project boundaries is assessed, whereafter a recommended action will be documented by PMT in the Change Log.
- **Change Approval:** the approval of a project change will be determined by the size and scope of the change requested. For low impact change requests which do not require formal approval by the EC, PMT will advise who must approve the change, be it PMT, the Managing Board or the ELIXIR-CONVERGE HoN Committee. If a formal change to the Grant Agreement is required then the PMT will use the information provided in the Change Log as an input to the formal amendment request that will be submitted to the EC. Only when a significant change is requested or a number of smaller requests have been received, will an amendment request be submitted to the EC, with no more than one amendment request per year.
- **Change Implementation:** the activities related to the implementation of approved changes will be documented in the Project Master File⁹.
- **Change Control:** new or open changes will be identified/reassessed during the weekly Project Management Meeting and during the Managing Board monthly meeting when needed.

⁸ <https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1abzvqo3sLsF1eoo7tGIYgsybAagyJAQInSvociU--fk/edit#gid=805749907>

⁹ https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1B_sK9O8uwAQEOGY-PRBGo8HbMgSrlKGE-MCrArKdXWo/edit#gid=0

4.4. Quality Management

The implementation and execution of ELIXIR-CONVERGE follows the principles of Horizon 2020 and European Commission (EC) rules and are more specifically defined in the Grant Agreement, the Description of Action and in the Consortium Agreement provisions. The procedures described in this section shall not replace any of the established agreements within the consortium or with the EC, or any of the EC guidelines for project implementation. The project will be managed according to EC best practice with a dedicated communications effort.

The Quality policy is based on the principles of Horizon 2020 and the EC rules related to scientific and operational quality; and will take into account the principles for Quality Management and Quality Assurance as laid down in the ISO 9000 framework.

Quality and its pursuit are regarded as important for every individual activity within the project. Criteria and quality standards of both the results of the project and the processes involved in their production need to be assured throughout the entire project.

ELIXIR-CONVERGE will explore the establishment and operation of a suite of high-quality communications channels, periodic project monitoring including work plan execution, quality assurance, data management, finance execution, innovation management activities, communication and risks.

ELIXIR-CONVERGE quality objectives are to:

- Ensure that all the project related activities and deliverables are fulfilling highest scientific and technical quality expectations and are following available quality and compliance standards issued by the EC under the Horizon 2020 funding scheme.
- To define the measures and the tools to be implemented by all consortium partners to meet these objectives and to provide support to partners to achieve high quality and to monitor adherence to the quality standards set for the project, in alignment with the DoA.
- Provide information on the processes in place to identify and manage major project risks.
- Ensure compliance with agreed Horizon 2020 and EC rules, applicable law and regulations, incl. but not limited to data privacy, handling of funds and ethics.

According to Horizon 2020 rules the Project Coordinator is also asked to promote gender equality in the project and science and society issues related to the research activities conducted within the project.

4.4.1. Quality policy

The generic quality policy adopted by ELIXIR-CONVERGE builds upon the following set of principles:

- Quality and its pursuit are regarded as important for every individual activity within the project.
- Criteria and standards by which the quality of both the results of the project and the processes involved in their production will be identified.
- Description of the tools, methods and techniques to be employed in order to ensure quality will be prepared.
- Allowance must be made for monitoring quality during the process and recording compliance and deviation.

Taking into consideration the overall quality policy, high quality standards are to be applied to all the work undertaken throughout the project.

4.4.2. Project quality control

The overall quality control of the project results includes the coordination of quality review for deliverables, prior to their submission to the EC.

It is crucial for the project to ensure that deliverables, as official results of the project, are reviewed and checked for quality. This may also apply to other outcomes of the project that are addressed to parties external to the project.

The present document is focusing only on the general methods implemented to ensure quality of written materials delivered to the EC and other partners external to the Consortium. A document produced in a project generally aims to provide information concerning the work, its progress or the derived results. Each document should thus be carefully drafted with rich content, a clear structure and a professional presentation. The three basic aspects for building quality into project documents are content, appearance and timing. It is generally accepted that the relative importance of each document varies, and it is important that overzealous quality criteria do not compromise timing if marginal benefit to the project is minimal.

For more information about the process, see section 7.1.3. Deliverable review process.

4.5. Configuration Management

4.5.1. Storage of project management artefacts

The Project Management Team have created a structured CONVERGE Google Drive to store the project management artefacts following the same folder convention per sub-folder. For any assistance with creating new folders, please contact converge-pm@elixir-europe.org.

4.5.2. Naming convention of project management artefacts

The latest version of a detailed, controlled Documents Version Policy outlining the project naming conventions and other configuration management guidance will be included in D6.2 Data Management Plan.

4.5.3. Versioning of project management artefacts

All project management artefacts are under version control, except for the project logs and checklists.

4.6. Communications Management

The communications management process determines how to communicate most efficiently and effectively to the various stakeholders. It defines and documents the communication items content, format, frequency, the audience and expected results. It also defines how to communicate project status and the assignment of activities to the various stakeholders, and the communication strategy for each stakeholder, based on their interests, expectations and influence in the project.

For more detailed information and guidance, please review the ELIXIR Communication Strategy¹⁰.

The project meetings identified in Table 5 below will be organised.

Table 5. Project Meetings

Meeting	Chair	Frequency
Project Kick-off Meeting	Project Management Meeting (PMT)	Once
Project Management Meetings	Project Management Team (PMT)	Weekly
Work Package Team Meetings	Work Package Leaders (WPLs)	weekly - monthly dependent on WP needs
Managing Board Meetings	Project Management Team (PMT)	Monthly (TC) Annually (F2F)
Workshop (co-design Node Impact Assessment Toolkit)	Project Management Team (PMT)	Once
General Assembly	Project Management Team (PMT)	Annually
Outreach and Dissemination meetings	Project Management Team (PMT)	Bi-annually
Industry engagement events	Project Management Team (PMT)	Annually
Mid-term Review Meeting	Project Management Team (PMT)	Once
Change Control Meeting	Project Management Team (PMT)	Ad Hoc
Project-End Review Meeting	Project Management Team (PMT)	Once

¹⁰ <https://elixir-europe.org/documents/elixir-communications-strategy>

The project reports listed in Table 6 below will be delivered.

Table 6. Project Reports.

Report	Responsible	Frequency
Periodic financial report	Project Coordinator	M12/M24/M42
Periodic technical report	Project Coordinator	M12/M24/M42
Ethics Report	Ethics Advisory Board (EAB)	M12/M24/M42 with Technical report
Project Status report	Work Package Leaders (WPLs)	Monthly (during WPL TC)
Project-End Report	Project Coordinator	With Project-End Review

4.6.1. Communication Plan

The ELIXIR-CONVERGE consortium will adopt the following approach to communications:

- Use of electronic mail as the main tool for communication within the consortium.
- Use of Slack as a less formal communication method where teams request it (As of March 2020, Channels currently available for each Work Package)
- Documentation of discussions, agreements and decisions made by phone is encouraged. Specifically, phone conferences should always have an agenda and minutes, which should be made available through the CONVERGE Google Drive.
- Several distribution lists have been initially created which can be used by any participant depending on the subject of the message. Additional lists may be created as the project evolves, if necessary. ELIXIR will be responsible for updating the below-mentioned lists with the information received from participants. When a list is used, care should be taken by participants to use the “reply to all” feature only when relevant. The table below shows the distribution lists created by the time of publishing this Handbook.

Table 7. Distribution Lists

Distribution list	Description
converge-admin@elixir-europe.org	CONVERGE PIs + admin contacts + CONVERGE PMT
converge-finance@elixir-europe.org	CONVERGE finance contacts + CONVERGE PMT
converge-legal@elixir-europe.org	CONVERGE legal contacts + CONVERGE PMT
converge-partners@elixir-europe.org	All people involved in CONVERGE: PIs + team members, admin, legal, finance + CONVERGE PMT
converge-pi@elixir-europe.org	All CONVERGE PIs + deputies (if requested) + CONVERGE PMT

converge-pm@elixir-europe.org	Hannah, Juan, Friederike, Nikki, Niklas
converge-scientific@elixir-europe.org	All CONVERGE scientific partners (signed up to WPs mailing lists) + CONVERGE PMT
converge-WP1@elixir-europe.org	WPLs, Deputy WPLs, all WP team members + CONVERGE PMT
converge-WP2@elixir-europe.org	WPLs, Deputy WPLs, all WP team members + CONVERGE PMT
converge-WP3@elixir-europe.org	WPLs, Deputy WPLs, all WP team members + CONVERGE PMT
converge-WP4@elixir-europe.org	WPLs, Deputy WPLs, all WP team members + CONVERGE PMT
converge-WP5@elixir-europe.org	WPLs, Deputy WPLs, all WP team members + CONVERGE PMT
converge-WP6@elixir-europe.org	WPLs, Deputy WPLs, all WP team members + CONVERGE PMT
converge-WP7@elixir-europe.org	WPLs, Deputy WPLs, all WP team members + CONVERGE PMT
converge-WP8@elixir-europe.org	WPLs, Deputy WPLs, all WP team members + CONVERGE PMT
converge-WP9@elixir-europe.org	WPLs, Deputy WPLs, all WP team members + CONVERGE PMT

4.6.2. Email guidelines

Good practice when using email is essential.

- Mails should be tagged when action is required (ACTION REQUIRED, FEEDBACK REQUIRED).
- Participants must respond promptly to any email received. When that is not possible, at least acknowledgement of receipt of all messages is strongly recommended, especially when answering an explicit request.
- Carefully consider whether “reply to all” is required.
- All emails sent to any of the mailing lists created so far should start with “CONVERGE:” in the subject section and senders should add the subject of the message.
- When individual messages between participants are exchanged, use of the same tag is strongly encouraged (e.g. CONVERGE: WPL meeting_agenda).
- Messages need to be concise but clear, especially when requests are made.
- Message text should include the content needed for the recipient to action the requests
- Deadlines must be made explicit.
- No relevant issues for the work to be performed should remain unclear.

4.6.3. File Exchange and Repository

A Google Drive instance has been created for ELIXIR-CONVERGE to be used as a repository of relevant information and files which facilitates the exchange of documents within the consortium (i.e. meeting minutes, documents in progress, final versions and other relevant reports or announcements). The ELIXIR-CONVERGE Google Drive also provides the possibility of discussion between participants through messages, maintenance of a calendar of meetings and events, upload of files, and tracking of important milestones and events at both the project and Work Package level.

- All beneficiaries have been enabled access to the ELIXIR-CONVERGE Google Drive once they have signed up to the mailing lists. New accesses can be requested by filling in the registration form¹¹
- The latest version of the ELIXIR-CONVERGE contact list is uploaded on the CONVERGE Google Drive, in the Registered Contacts section of the Project Monitoring spreadsheet¹². The up-to-date participants' contact information with clear information of who is included in every mailing list mentioned above will be based on the periodic updates by each of the Work Package Leaders.
- The use of de facto standards based on MS Office-compatible files for electronic document exchange among participants is required when possible. PDF format can alternatively be used to avoid excessive size of files when no editing is required.

ELIXIR-CONVERGE uses Google Drive as a project management tool that is simultaneously used as a document management system. The ELIXIR-CONVERGE Google Drive provides a place to store, secure and organise the consortium documentation which helps to ultimately control the quality of documents and conformity of processes.

The tool has capabilities available to set permissions on a file or folder. These clear access rights can be rapidly degraded or defeated entirely by the sysadmin (coordinator) of the consortium. Users with proper visibility rights and access permission can fuel quality control of the project.

Additionally, a document version history is an efficient way to track who has edited files and when. This platform allows users to revert to an earlier version if the file becomes corrupted or if errors are introduced.

With the notification feature available, each person with permission can invite other consortium participants on document edits and to track changes to a document stored in a shared folder simultaneously.

ELIXIR-CONVERGE uses Google Drive to manage quality of the documents and processes by enhancing the centralization of digital assets, promote maintenance of quality and support backup and data protection.

¹¹https://docs.google.com/forms/d/e/1FAIpQLSd_WGKAjFgeSmZMogsO2_BOz4lvp7Uh5ZYqb48ooYqn5rfEvQ/viewform

¹² <https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1abzvqo3sLsF1eoo7tGIYgsybAagyJAQlnSvociU--fk/edit#gid=1726970740>

Any publication in ELIXIR-CONVERGE is governed by Article 29 of the Grant Agreement and Article 7.5 of the Consortium Agreement. Scientific Publications and Communication to the public are covered by the Communication Plan (section 4.6.1, above) created by WP4.

The Documents Versioning Policy outlined in Section 4.5.2. (Configuration Management), is key to clean and consistent archiving; especially towards the mid/end phase of the project when an increasing number of digital outputs and documents are created. Using the same tag for email subjects and for the documentations in attachments, fuels clear communication and leads to reduced email burden and duplication of work.

4.6.4. Dissemination

Dissemination is an important activity for all EC projects, a fact that is recognised in the project Grant Agreement¹³, which requires that we make our scientific work and results openly available, as early as possible and in a form that is easily accessible, understandable and reusable.

All partners must follow the dissemination circulation procedure set out in Clause 7.5.2.2 of the Consortium Agreement¹⁴.

The Commission also provide a Horizon 2020 guide to communicating EU research and innovation for project participants¹⁵.

4.6.5. Open Access policy and requirements

Article 29.2 of the EC Annotated Model Grant Agreement (AMGA)¹⁶ details the obligations related to the provision of open access to scientific publications.

We must ensure open access (free, online access for any user) to all peer-reviewed scientific publications relating to our ELIXIR-CONVERGE project results.

Further explanations can be found in the EC Annotated Model Grant Agreement. The EC have also prepared the following guide to help steer this process.

Published articles (peer-reviewed or not) have to be submitted to PMT in PDF format. The document(s) will be made available to the consortium on the ELIXIR-CONVERGE Google Drive in the Articles folder¹⁷ and listed in the publications and dissemination activities spreadsheet¹⁸.

¹³ https://drive.google.com/open?id=1hyHR5399GOWNDi3EsDOLCr_TEohCRXwp

¹⁴ A fully executed copy of the CA has been circulated to all partners

¹⁵ https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/other/gm/h2020-guide-comm_en.pdf

¹⁶ https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/grants_manual/amga/h2020-amga_en.pdf

¹⁷ <https://drive.google.com/open?id=1MuGeU21sfV6BwReSqoolT2boiM2kqqTq>

¹⁸ https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1OGNHLElusig9BpT63NGeh_qRY9cMpKUBmVEGjollLumQ/edit#gid=1159678595

4.6.6. EU Funding Acknowledgement

As set out in Article 38 of the Grant Agreement¹⁹, unless the Commission requests or agrees otherwise or unless it is impossible, any communication activity related to the CONVERGE project (including in electronic form, via social media, etc.) and any infrastructure, equipment and major results funded by the grant must:

(a) display the EU emblem and

To be used for ELIXIR-CONVERGE:

- Download the EU emblem²⁰ in different versions and formats
- When displayed together with another logo, the EU emblem must have appropriate prominence.
- For the purposes of our obligations under Article 38 of the GA, the beneficiaries may use the EU emblem without first obtaining approval from the Commission.

(b) include the following text:

ELIXIR-CONVERGE acknowledgement:

For communication activities:

"This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 871075".

For infrastructure, equipment and major results:

"This [infrastructure][equipment][insert type of result] is part of a project that has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 871075".

If it is not possible to use this exact statement (e.g. if numerous grants are cited), please ensure that at least the grant's name (ELIXIR-CONVERGE) and the grant agreement number (871075) are specified in the Acknowledgements or Funding Statement of the publication, as this helps with detecting articles using text-mining.

- A formal acknowledgement of EC support

¹⁹ <https://drive.google.com/file/d/1gLhclTzFumCGuobTsZBPcZKFcPB2m5Qn/view>

²⁰ https://europa.eu/european-union/about-eu/symbols/flag_en

Disclaimer excluding Commission responsibility: Any communication activity related to the action must indicate that it reflects only the author's view and that the Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

ELIXIR-CONVERGE disclaimer:

This communication reflects the views of the authors and neither the European Union or any Associated Partners are liable for any use that may be made of the information contained herein.

4.6.7. Project Branding

The ELIXIR-CONVERGE project must follow the ELIXIR branding and communication guidelines. The ELIXIR branding guidelines, font and project logo are all available on the project Google Drive²¹.

The branding and style guide should be used in all project communications without alteration. For any questions related to branding and communications please contact Xènia Pérez Sitjà, xenia.sitja@elixir-europe.org.

Figure 1. The ELIXIR-CONVERGE logo

4.6.8. Project Website

The project webpages²² are housed on the ELIXIR website and provide an overview of the project, consortium and Board members, and the project timeline. In addition, visitors can find details of

²¹ <https://drive.google.com/drive/u/o/folders/1ZZxGQMw-4fgUIUz-gEdGg3INnPBfpzf4>

²² <https://elixir-europe.org/about-us/how-funded/eu-projects/converge>

upcoming events, and our project outputs. Publications, press releases and submitted public deliverables are also available via the site.

For any updates to the project website, contact Martin Cook, martin.cook@elixir-europe.org.

4.6.9. Social Media

ELIXIR-CONVERGE does not have dedicated social media accounts, instead, the ELIXIR accounts will be used with dedicated project hashtags on the following platforms:

Twitter: #ELIXIRCONVERGE

LinkedIn: #ELIXIRCONVERGE

4.6.10. Weekly Brief

The ELIXIR Hub publishes a weekly email update called the Weekly Brief. All CONVERGE project partners who have signed up to receive this have now been added to the mailing list and receive it weekly on a Monday morning. Every issue provides the recipient with the option to update their preferences or unsubscribe from the list. Content for the Brief is gathered by the ELIXIR Hub communications team. All project partners are encouraged to suggest any project content ideas either by email to the communications team or during the monthly Programme TCs/Managing Board TCs.

Content ideas can be emailed to info@elixir-europe.org.

4.6.11. Templates

Presentations for internal or external communication should use the ELIXIR-CONVERGE PowerPoint/Google Slide template.

All internal and external documents should use the ELIXIR-CONVERGE Word/Google Doc template.

All templates are available on the ELIXIR-CONVERGE Google Drive in the Templates folder²³.

All presentations, posters, media briefings and event documentation should display the European flag, besides the project logo. In line with the European Commission's policy on corporate visual identity, Horizon 2020 is being promoted as a verbal brand, meaning no 'visual mark' or logotype is needed. More information about displaying the correct logos and funding acknowledgements can be found in the EU Funding Acknowledgement section above, but for any questions, contact should be made with Xènia Pérez Sitjà, xenia.sitja@elixir-europe.org.

A deliverable template has been prepared and can be found in the Templates folder on the ELIXIR-CONVERGE Google Drive²⁴, but please note that an individually tailored template has been created by the Project Management Team for all project deliverables and are circulated in

²³ <https://drive.google.com/drive/u/o/folders/1cxSNL4oxRVw-dsLPUI7p6QplKdifD8GR>

²⁴ <https://drive.google.com/drive/u/o/folders/1cxSNL4oxRVw-dsLPUI7p6QplKdifD8GR>

the monthly project monitoring emails which are automatically sent to WPLs. All Deliverable Authors shall use the approved deliverable template for the production of deliverables. For more information about how to prepare a deliverable report, please see section 7.1. (Deliverable).

Under the Consortium Agreement Mandate²⁵ various legal agreement templates can be found in the Appendices including: CDA (one-way and two-way), Advisory Agreement, Form of Accession (new partners). If you feel a legal agreement is needed within the project, please contact converge-pm@elixir-europe.org who will be able to advise.

5. PROJECT MANAGEMENT STRUCTURE AND RESPONSIBILITIES

Figure 2. Management Structure. Part A.

5.1. Description of Project Roles and Responsibilities

In the following section, the roles of major stakeholders in the ELIXIR-CONVERGE project are described alongside the responsibilities, expectations, rights and duties of each participant in the project.

5.1.1. Project Coordinator

Name:	Niklas Blomberg
Organisation:	ELIXIR Hub
Email:	niklas.blomberg@elixir-europe.org

²⁵A fully executed copy of the CA has been circulated to all partners

Role:	<p>The ELIXIR Hub is appointed as Coordinator. The Coordinator shall act through a designated Representative, Niklas Blomberg.</p> <p>The Coordinator is and shall be a central point of contact between the Beneficiaries and the EC in particular regarding the management of the Grant.</p> <p>Specific duties: Legal signatory, legal responsibility for contract, budget oversight and control, submission of deliverables and milestones to EC, chair of GA and MB. The Coordinator is supported by the Project Management Team in regards to financial and contractual administration of the project.</p>
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5.1.2. General Assembly

The General Assembly (GA) is composed of representatives of all project beneficiaries that have delegated the decision making to the HoN. The GA will be informed of the project progress in a timely manner (Board meeting minutes circulated to all partners).

If necessary, each Beneficiary shall also be entitled to nominate a replacement Representative in the event that the original Representative is unable to attend any scheduled meetings of the General Assembly.

Meetings

The GA will meet face to face once a year with the Managing Board at the ELIXIR All Hands meeting to be updated on the project progress and plans.

A Representative of the Coordinator shall chair the General Assembly. The Chairperson of the General Assembly shall:

- be responsible for the convening of meetings, preparation and distribution of the agenda and minutes for meetings of the General Assembly; and
- chair meetings of the General Assembly.

Where the Chairperson of the General Assembly cannot attend a General Assembly meeting, the General Assembly shall nominate a replacement to chair the meeting for the purposes of such meeting of the General Assembly only, provided that the replacement must be a Representative. Such replacement shall be deemed Chairperson of the General Assembly.

Table 8. General Assembly members

Participant	GA member
ELIXIR HUB/ EMBL-EBI	Niklas Blomberg / Johanna McEntyre
VIB	Frederik Coppens

SIB	Christine Durinx
UCY	Vasilis Promponas
CING	George Spyrou
UOCHB	Jiri Vondrasek
HITS	Wolfgang Muller
DTU	Soren Brunak
UT	Hedi Peterson
BSC	Alfonso Valencia
CSC	Tommi Nyronen
INRAE	Anne Francoise Adam-Blondon
CNRS	Claudine Medigue
BSRC	Babis Savakis
ATHENA-RIC	Theodore Dalamagas
CERTH	Christos Ouzounis
TTK	Balazs Gyorffy
UCD	Denis Shields
WEIZMANN	Robrt Fluhr
CNR	Graziano Pesole

UNILU	Reinhard Schneider
DTL-PROJECTS	Celia Van Gelder
UiB	Inge Jonassen
INESC-ID	Mario J. Gaspar da Silva
IGC	Pedro Fernandes
UU	Bengt Persson
UL	Brane Leskosek
UNIMAN	Carole Goble
UCAM	Anne Ferguson-Smith
CRG	Jordi Rambla
UP	Attila Gyenesei
UCT	Nicola Mulder
UKZN	Tulio de Oliveira
ALU-FR	Bjørn Gruning
DKFZ	Oliver Stegle
EKUT	Oliver Kohlbacher
FPS	Joaquin Dopazo
ISCIII	Isabel Cuesta de la Plaza
CSIC	Iñaki Comas

IBCH	Krzysztof Kurowski
UOXF	Oliver Pybus
UCPH	Søren Brunak
GOG	Alexander Degelsegger-Márquez
HRI	Ruben Kok

See Clause 11.3 of the Consortium Agreement²⁶ for further information regarding the General Assembly.

5.1.3. Heads of Nodes Committee (HoN)

The Heads of Nodes Committee (HoN) is composed of the Heads of each ELIXIR Node and is chaired by the ELIXIR Director. The Heads of Nodes Committee is the senior scientific decision making body and management team within ELIXIR: together with the Director, the HoN Committee develops the ELIXIR Scientific Programme, decides on grant application strategies and oversees ELIXIR technical activities. The HoN Committee takes the leading role in developing the strategy for ELIXIR services, monitoring of performance as well as identification of service gaps.

As the senior scientific management team for ELIXIR, the HoN Committee will also maintain the overview of the technical and scientific activities in the infrastructure to ensure scientific excellence and impact. The Managing Board (see below) will update the HoN quarterly on the project progress and the HoN will be the decision making body for this project with one vote per Node.

The Heads of Nodes Committee (HoN) shall be responsible for the determination of policies and decision making in relation to the overall management of the Action and finding amicable solutions for any unresolved disputes between the Beneficiaries relating to the execution of the Action.

Meetings

One HoN meeting per annum will be co-located with the project General Assembly at the ELIXIR All Hands meeting.

A Representative of the Coordinator shall chair the HoN meeting. The Chairperson of the HoN meeting shall:

²⁶ A fully executed copy of the CA has been circulated to all partners

- be responsible for the convening of meetings, preparation and distribution of the agenda and minutes for meetings of the HoN; and
- chair meetings of the HoN.

Where the Chairperson of the HoN cannot attend a HoN meeting, the HoN shall nominate a replacement to chair the meeting for the purposes of such a meeting of the HoN only, provided that the replacement must be a Representative. Such replacement shall be deemed Chairperson of the HoN.

The Heads of Nodes Committee meets at least every twelve (12) months at venues to be agreed, or at any other time at the request of any of the Beneficiaries. Such other meetings may be held via face-to-face or telephone or video conference allowing votes to be submitted verbally.

See Clause 11.3 of the Consortium Agreement²⁷ for further information regarding the Heads of Nodes.

Table 9. Heads of Nodes (HoN) Committee

Node	HoN	Deputy
Belgium	Dr Frederik Coppens	Dr Kim de Ruyck
Czech Republic	Dr Jiří Vondrášek	Prof. Ludek Matyska
Denmark	Prof. Søren Brunak	N/A
EMBL-EBI	Dr Rolf Apweiler and Dr Ewan Birney	Dr Johanna McEntyre
Estonia	Prof. Jaak Vilo	Dr Hedi Peterson
Finland	Dr Tommi Nyrönen	Dr Ilkka Lappalainen
France	Dr Jacques van Helden and Prof. Claudine Médigue	Prof. Anne-Francoise Adam-Blondon
Germany	Prof. Andreas Tauch	Prof. Alfred Pühler
Greece	Dr Martin Reczko	Dr Christoforos Nikolaou
Hungary	Dr Balázs Gyórfy	N/A
Ireland	Prof. Denis Shields	Dr Colm Ryan
Israel	Prof. Michal Linial and Dr Dan Ben-Avraham	N/A
Italy	Prof. Graziano Pesole	Prof. Silvio Tosatto
Luxembourg	Dr Reinhard Schneider	Dr Wei Gu
Netherlands	Prof. Jaap Heringa	Dr Morris Swertz

²⁷ A fully executed copy of the CA has been circulated to all partners

Norway	Prof. Inge Jonassen	Dr Nils Peder Willassen
Portugal	Dr Mário Silva (ELIXIR Portugal)	Dr Ana Portugal Melo
Slovenia	Prof. Brane Leskošek	N/A
Spain	Prof. Alfonso Valencia	Dr Salvador Capella-Gutierrez
Sweden	Prof. Bengt Persson	Dr Jessica Lindvall
Switzerland	Prof. Ron Appel and Dr Christine Durinx	N/A
United Kingdom	Prof. Carole Goble and Prof. Neil Hall	N/A
Cyprus (Observer)	Dr George Spyrou	Dr Vasilis Promponas

5.1.4. Work Package Leaders

The Work Package Leads (WPLs) are responsible for overseeing the technical progress of the project and ensure interoperability and alignment of co-dependent tasks across work packages. They are also responsible for presenting the work carried out by the WP to the European Commission and for the content of their WP activities within the periodic reports.

WPLs are responsible for the proper execution of the DoA and the implementation of the decisions of the HoN and Managing Board. The Work Package Leaders collectively make up the Managing Board. They are expected to identify issues, risks and opportunities within the technical tasks of the Project and take appropriate actions to ensure the project delivers the anticipated benefits both at work package and project level. Risks or opportunities that cut across more than one work package should, together with a suggested action, be elevated to the Managing Board during the monthly meetings. The WPLs, as the Managing Board and via the Coordinator, report on the project progress to the HoNs at least every 6 months.

WPLs are responsible for filtering project information from the Managing Board meetings to their work packages via their dedicated WP distribution lists, during their regular meetings, or via other communication means they deem fit, e.g. Slack. WPLs are responsible for scheduling their own WP meetings, creating and circulating an agenda, and taking and disseminating minutes.

In case of beneficiaries not performing their roles, WPLs are expected to promptly document the situation and raise it with the PMT in order to swiftly address reputational or technical risk for the consortium.

Where a WPL is unable to host one of their Work Package meetings or attend a Managing Board meeting they may deputise to their predefined Deputy Work Package Leader.

Contact: converge-wpl@elixir-europe.org

For more information, please refer to the ELIXIR Hub document Work Package Leader's Good Practice Guide²⁸. Please be aware, as of 15/04/2020, that this is currently a working draft.

5.1.5. Managing Board

The Managing Board (MB) is composed of the Project Coordinator and the Work Package Leaders and is responsible for ensuring alignment and coordination across Work Packages and for the successful execution of the project.

The Managing Board shall be responsible for the overall execution of the Action, the quality of the Action, alignment across all Work Packages, decision making and the initial finding of amicable solutions for any disputes between the Beneficiaries relating to the execution of the Action. The MB will ensure the smooth operation of the Action and guarantee that all efforts are focused towards the Action Objectives, Deliverables and Milestones. This will be achieved by regular meetings, at least every month, and thorough reviews of progress reports. It will also ensure that all Beneficiaries are regularly updated on the scientific progress. The responsibilities are fully detailed in the ELIXIR-CONVERGE Consortium Agreement²⁹.

MB members shall have named deputies to ensure proper representation in all meetings.

The Managing Board will be supported by the Project Management Team (PMT).

Meetings

The Managing Board will meet at least every month. In addition to the monthly teleconferences, the MB shall meet twice a year face to face making use of regular ELIXIR events such as the ELIXIR All Hands and HoN face to face meetings.

A Representative of the Project Coordinator will act as the chairperson of the Managing Board (the "Chairperson of the Managing Board") and shall:

- a) with assistance from the Project Management Team, be responsible for the convening of meetings, preparation and distribution of the agenda and minutes for meetings of the Managing Board; and
- b) chair meetings of the Managing Board.

Where a Work Package Leader is unable to attend a meeting they may send their predefined Deputy Work Package Leader.

See Clause 11.4 of the Consortium Agreement³⁰ for further information regarding the Managing Board.

Table 10. Managing Board members

²⁸https://docs.google.com/document/d/1jZAhcO4wYMsm8pdd22vO7wNaiowg83H7Fm_Ro8EL_FQ/edit#heading=h.d7mglvqj5e18

²⁹ A fully executed copy of the CA has been circulated to all partners

³⁰ A fully executed copy of the CA has been circulated to all partners

Role	Managing Board Member	Managing Board Deputy
Project Coordinator	Niklas Blomberg (ELIXIR Hub)	Jerry Lanfear (ELIXIR Hub)
WP1 Leader	Niclas Jareborg (UU/SU)	Bengt Persson (UU)
WP2 Leader	Celia van Gelder (DTL-Projects)	Brane Leskosek (UL)
WP3 Leader	Frederik Coppens (VIB)	Wolfgang Muller (HITS)
WP4 Leader	Andrew Smith (ELIXIR Hub)	Corinne Martin (ELIXIR Hub)
WP5 Leader	Anne-Francoise Adam-Blondon (INRAE)	Salvador Capella-Gutierrez (BSC)
WP6 Leader	Juan Arenas Marquez (ELIXIR Hub)	Hannah Hurst (ELIXIR Hub)
WP7 Leader	Thomas Keane (EMBL-EBI)	Jordi Rambla (CRG)
WP8 Leader	Guy Cochrane (EMBL-EBI)	Jeena Rajan (EMBL-EBI)
Wp9 Leader	Aitana Neves (SIB)	Erik Hjerde (UiB/UiT)

Contact: converge-wpl@elixir-europe.org

5.1.6. SAB (Scientific Advisory Board)

ELIXIR-CONVERGE will make use of ELIXIR's Scientific Advisory Board (SAB) for progress review. The ELIXIR SAB regularly review the ELIXIR Nodes and will provide recommendations for the scientific strategy of this project in the context of overall ELIXIR Strategy as well as individual Node strategies. The ELIXIR SAB includes experts in the biological and biomedical life science area whose backgrounds cover science and industry and are elected by the ELIXIR Board.

Meetings

The SAB meet in person once a year in December and hold one teleconference in summer. They provide direct feedback to the ELIXIR Board. The ELIXIR SAB will meet with the ELIXIR Director and MB representatives face to face (yearly ELIXIR SAB F2F meeting).

See Clause 11.6 of the Consortium Agreement³¹ for further information regarding the SAB.

Table 11. SAB members

³¹ A fully executed copy of the CA has been circulated to all partners

SAB member	Affiliation
Prof. Philip Bourne	University of Virginia, USA
Prof. Ana Sofia Carvalho	Catholic University of Portugal, Portugal
Dr Jennifer Gardy	Bill & Melinda Gates Foundation, USA
Dr Robert Gentleman	Harvard Medical School, USA
Prof. Melissa Haendel	Oregon Health and Science University, USA
Prof. Larry Hunter	University of Colorado, USA
Prof. Elina Ikonen	University of Helsinki, Finland
Dr Janet Kelso (Vice-Chair)	Max Planck Institute for Evolutionary Anthropology, Germany
Prof. Nicola Mulder	UCT Computational Biology Group (NBN), South Africa
Dr BF Francis Ouellette (Chair)	Origin Bioinformatics, Canada
Dr Susan E. Wallace	University of Leicester, UK
Dr Doreen Ware	USDA ARS, Cold Spring Harbor Laboratory, USA

Contact: sab@elixir-europe.org

5.1.7. IAC (Industry Advisory Committee)

The ELIXIR Industry Advisory Committee (IAC) provide the ELIXIR Director and HoN with high-level strategic advice on industry needs and opportunities within the ELIXIR programme to promote open innovation and public-private research partnership. The IAC comprises experts from the bioinformatics industry, including SMEs and large multinational companies (appointed by ELIXIR Board).

Meetings

The IAC meets face to face once per year. The ELIXIR IAC will meet with the ELIXIR Director and MB representatives face to face (collocated with the ELIXIR SAB F2F meeting) and via TC as and when required.

See Clause 11.7 of the Consortium Agreement³² for further information regarding the IAC.

³² A fully executed copy of the CA has been circulated to all partners

Table 12. IAC members

Name	Affiliation
Ian Barrett	AstraZeneca, UK
Thomas Exner	Seven Past Nine GmbH, Germany
Andreas Kremer	ITTM, Luxembourg
Natalia Jiménez Lozano (Vice-Chair)	Atos, UK
Klaus Maisinger	Illumina, UK
Filip Pattyn	Ontoforce, Belgium
Jörg Peplies	Ribocon GmbH, Germany
Elizabeth Reynolds	General Bioinformatics, UK
María Rodríguez Martínez	IBM, Switzerland
Philippe Sanseau	GlaxoSmithKline, UK
Catherine Sirven	Bayer, France
Abel Ureta-Vidal (Chair)	CMS Ventures, UK

Contact: iac@elixir-europe.org

5.1.8. ELIXIR-CONVERGE Implementation Team

The ELIXIR-CONVERGE Implementation Team will be chaired by WP5 and attended with the Demonstrator Projects and a representative from each Work Package, to oversee the support provided to the different projects and to feed back to the Managing Board. This cross-functional team will release the project work plan following the leadership of the Managing Board. At the same time, they will contribute to identifying exploitable assets, issues, risks, opportunities and impediments early in the project which is critical to delivering the expected impact in the project timeframe.

Meetings

The Implementation Team will meet monthly via TC.

5.1.9. Project Management Team (PMT)

The Project Management Team (PMT) will be led by the ELIXIR Project Management Office and leverage their experience and processes for managing large, international consortia to ensure

timely delivery and effective communication and collaboration across WPs, and towards internal and external stakeholders.

Name:	Juan Arenas Marquez / Hannah Hurst / Nikki Coutts
Organisation:	ELIXIR Hub
Email:	converge-pm@elixir-europe.org
Role:	<p>The PM Team assists the Managing Board. It is responsible for the day-to-day execution of the Project, providing the necessary project management support to deliver the Project.</p> <p>In particular, the PM Team is responsible for the following tasks and activities:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● implementation of all management and organisational tasks ● scheduling of decisions ● monitoring the achievement of set milestones ● timely submission of deliverables ● organisation and documentation of the meetings of the Consortium Bodies ● dissemination of all relevant information and action items across the Consortium ● accounting for all financial aspects of the Project and ensuring timely submission of all required reports to the EC.

The PM Team will support and report on the execution of the project work plan and budget utilisation, providing the mechanism to identify and manage project risks and opportunities.

A consortium communication strategy will be established (WP4) making appropriate use of digital resources. Communication dynamics will be promoted across the project, keeping the right level of engagement among stakeholders. Specific collaboration tools will be enabled from the first stages of the Project. These tools will guarantee the means for efficient communication within the Consortium fulfilling internal communication needs, and external stakeholders needs (WP4).

Meetings

The PM Team meet on a weekly basis.

5.1.10. Task Leaders

Each Work Package is broken down into tasks and sub-tasks.

Each Task Lead is responsible for prompt and on time performance and fulfilment of the assigned task and subtask as per the Description of Action (DoA) in cooperation with all task participants and liaising with the respective WPL.

The Task Leads must ensure that the fulfilment of their task activities are accomplished in due time in line with the commitments identified in the DoA.

Task Leads shall promptly notify the WPL of any significant problem or delay likely to affect the completion of the assigned task.

Each participant must ensure timely contribution to the allocated tasks, as requested by each Task Leads and/or WPLs. Any encountered issue should be discussed with the Task Lead and, if needed, escalated to the WPL level.

The designated Task Leaders are presented in Table 13 below.

Table 14. Task Leaders

Task #	Task Leader	Email	Organisation
T1.1	Bengt Persson / Niclas Jareborg	bengt.persson@icm.uu.se / niclas.jareborg@nbis.se	UU (LTP - SU)
T1.2	Guy Cochrane	cochrane@ebi.ac.uk	EMBL-EBI
T1.3	Silvio Tosatto	g.pesole@ibiom.cnr.it	CNR (LTP - UNIPD)
T1.4	Jiri Vondrasek	jiri.vondrasek@uochb.cas.cz	UOCHB
T2.1	Anne Ferguson-Smith	afsmith@gen.cam.ac.uk	UCAM
T2.2	Celia van Gelder	celia.van.gelder@dtls.nl	DTL-Projects
T2.3	Brane Leskosek	brane.leskosek@mf.uni-lj.si	UL
T2.4	Patricia Palagi	patricia.palagi@sib.swiss	SIB
T3.1	Carole Goble	carole.goble@manchester.ac.uk	UNIMAN
T3.2	Inge Jonassen	Inge.Jonassen@ii.uib.no	UiB
T3.3	Rob Hooft	rob.hooft@dtls.nl	DTL-Projects

T3.4	Pinar Alper	pinar.alper@uni.lu	UNILU
T4.1	Andrew Smith	andrew.smith@elixir-europe.org	ELIXIR Hub
T4.2	Katharina Lauer	katharina.lauer@elixir-europe.org	ELIXIR Hub
T4.3	Corinne Martin	corinne.martin@elixir-europe.org	ELIXIR Hub
T4.4	Corinne Martin	corinne.martin@elixir-europe.org	ELIXIR Hub
T4.5	Corinne Martin	corinne.martin@elixir-europe.org	ELIXIR Hub
T5.1	Anne-Francoise Adam-Blondon	anne-francoise.adam-blondon@inrae.fr	INRAE
T5.2	Salvador Capella-Gutierrez	salvador.capella@bsc.es	BSC
T5.3	Inge Jonassen	Inge.Jonassen@ii.uib.no	UiB
T5.4	Brane Leskosek	brane.leskosek@mf.uni-lj.si	UL
T6.1	Juan Arenas Marquez	juan.arenas@elixir-europe.org	ELIXIR Hub
T6.2	Hannah Hurst	hannah.hurst@elixir-europe.org	ELIXIR Hub
T6.3	Hannah Hurst	hannah.hurst@elixir-europe.org	ELIXIR Hub
T6.4	Susanna Repo	susanna.repo@elixir-europe.org	ELIXIR Hub
T7.1	Thomas Keane	tk2@ebi.ac.uk	EMBL-EBI
T7.2	Jordi Rambla	jordi.rambla@crg.eu	CRG
T7.3	Tommi Nyronen	tommi.nyronen@csc.fi	CSC
T7.4	Salvador Capella-Gutierrez	salvador.capella@bsc.es	BSC
T8.1	Guy Cochrane	cochrane@ebi.ac.uk	EMBL-EBI
T8.2	Guy Cochrane	cochrane@ebi.ac.uk	EMBL-EBI

T8.3	Guy Cochrane	cochrane@ebi.ac.uk	EMBL-EBI
T9.1	Carla Cummins	carlac@ebi.ac.uk	EMBL-EBI
T9.2	Aitana Neves	Aitana.Neves@sib.swiss	SIB
T9.3	Tulio de Oliveira	deoliveira@ukzn.ac.za	UKZN
T9.4	Beatriz Serrano-Solano	beatrizserrano.galaxy@gmail.com	ALU-FR

The most up-to-date Task Leader list is available on the CONVERGE Google Drive³³.

5.1.11. Deliverable Authors

The following Deliverable Lead Authors are responsible for the production of the deliverables according to the deliverable preparation procedure defined in Section 7.1 (Deliverables).

Table 15. Deliverable Lead Authors

Deliverable #	Name	Email	Organisation
D1.1	Niclas Jareborg	niclas.jareborg@nbis.se	UU
D1.2	Graziano Pesole	g.pesole@ibiom.cnr.it	CNR
D1.3	Jiri Vondrašek	jiri.vondrasek@uochb.cas.cz	UOCHB
D1.4	Niclas Jareborg	niclas.jareborg@nbis.se	UU
D2.1	Alexia Cardona	ac812@cam.ac.uk	UCAM
D2.2	Celia van Gelder	celia.van.gelder@dtls.nl	DTL-Projects
D2.3	Brane Leskošek	brane.leskosek@mf.uni-lj.si	UL
D2.4	Brane Leskošek	brane.leskosek@mf.uni-lj.si	UL
D2.5	Patricia Palagi	Patricia.Palagi@sib.swiss	SIB
D3.1	Carole Goble	carole.goble@manchester.ac.uk	UNIMAN
D3.2	Inge Jonassen	Inge.Jonassen@uib.no	UiB
D3.3	Celia van Gelder	celia.van.gelder@dtls.nl	DTL-Projects

³³

https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1B_sKgQ8uwAQEOGY-PRBG08HbMgSrIKGE-MCrArKdXWo/edit#gid=1122316636

D3.4	Pinar Alper	pinar.alper@uni.lu	UNILU
D3.5	Frederik Coppens	frcop@psb.vib-ugent.be	VIB
D4.1	Corinne Martin	corinne.martin@elixir-europe.org	ELIXIR Hub
D4.2	Corinne Martin	corinne.martin@elixir-europe.org	ELIXIR Hub
D4.3	Corinne Martin	corinne.martin@elixir-europe.org	ELIXIR Hub
D5.1	Anne-Françoise Adam-Blondon	anne-francoise.adam-blondon@inrae.fr	INRAE
D5.2	Graziano Pesole	g.pesole@ibiom.cnr.it	CNR
D5.3	Brane Leskošek	brane.leskosek@mf.uni-lj.si	UL
D5.4	Inge Jonassen	Inge.Jonassen@uib.no	UiB
D5.5	Salvador Capella-Gutierrez	salvador.capella@bsc.es	BSC
D6.1	Hannah Hurst	hannah.hurst@elixir-europe.org	ELIXIR Hub
D6.2	Juan Arenas-Marquez	juan.arenas@elixir-europe.org	ELIXIR Hub
D6.3	Juan Arenas-Marquez Nikki Coutts	juan.arenas@elixir-europe.org nikki.coutts@elixir-europe.org	ELIXIR Hub
D6.4	Juan Arenas-Marquez Nikki Coutts	juan.arenas@elixir-europe.org nikki.coutts@elixir-europe.org	ELIXIR Hub
D7.1	Thomas Keane	tk2@ebi.ac.uk	EMBL-EBI
D7.2	Jordi Rambla	jordi.rambla@crg.eu	CRG
D7.3	Tommi Nyrönen	tommi.nyronen@csc.fi	CSC
D7.4	Salvador Capella-Gutierrez	salvador.capella@bsc.es	BSC
D8.1	Guy Cochrane	cochrane@ebi.ac.uk	EMBL-EBI
D8.2	Guy Cochrane	cochrane@ebi.ac.uk	EMBL-EBI
D8.3	Guy Cochrane	cochrane@ebi.ac.uk	EMBL-EBI
D8.4	Guy Cochrane	cochrane@ebi.ac.uk	EMBL-EBI
D8.5	Guy Cochrane	cochrane@ebi.ac.uk	EMBL-EBI
D9.1	Carla Cummins	carlac@ebi.ac.uk	EMBL-EBI

D9.2	Aitana Neves	Aitana.Neves@sib.swiss	SIB
D9.3	Tulio de Oliveira	deoliveira@ukzn.ac.za	UKZN

The most up-to-date list of Deliverable Authors ist is available on the CONVERGE Google Drive³⁴.

5.2 How and when the project bodies meet

The Coordinator, supported by the PM Team, are responsible for convening meetings of the management and governance bodies at the CONVERGE overall level (i.e. GA, MB, SIAB), complying with the minimum frequency of ordinary meetings as defined in the CONVERGE Consortium Agreement (CA) and detailed above. Work Package leaders have the responsibility of calling meetings within their respective WPs as needed.

According to the CA, the bodies of the CONVERGE governance will have at least the following meeting frequency:

Table 16. Meeting Frequency

Meeting Frequency	Project Bodies
Weekly	PM (TC)
Monthly	MB (TC), Implementation Team (TC)
Bi-Annually	MB (F2F), SAB (F2F & TC)
Annually	GA (F2F), HoN (F2F), IAC (F2F)
As needed	HoN (TC or F2F), IAC (TC)

Organisation of meetings comprises the following tasks:

- professional convocation and on time distribution of the agenda according to the terms of the Grant Agreement;
- organisation of facilities or conference venues with the required infrastructure and catering, to ensure the smooth running of the conference (when face-to-face);
- organisation and steering of decision-making processes at CONVERGE meetings
- distribution of minutes following the meeting and follow-up of points agreed at the meetings.

³⁴https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1B_sK9O8uwAQEOGY-PRBGo8HbMgSrlKGE-MCrArKdXWo/edit#gid=858182447

5.3. Beneficiaries

5.3.1. How Beneficiaries change their representatives to the General Assembly (GA)

Beneficiaries' representatives in the General Assembly (GA) are expected to be maintained throughout the project. Any representative in the GA may nominate a substitute to attend and vote at any meeting. In that respect, any change in a representative in the GA must be informed by the original representative, in writing (including electronic mail), to the Chair (Coordinator) at least one week before an ordinary meeting of the GA takes place, indicating the reason for substitution and identifying the new representative.

GA members can be accompanied by other representatives of their respective institutions at meetings, but only one vote per institution is allowed in the GA.

5.3.2. What are the main Beneficiaries' responsibilities?

Beneficiaries must use all reasonable endeavours to perform and fulfil, promptly, and on time, all of their obligations under the Grant Agreement and the Consortium Agreement, to accomplish the purpose and objectives of the CONVERGE project and act in cooperation and mutual trust. Beneficiaries shall also provide their respective contributions to deliverables, information, and reports as required by the WPLs, the MB, the PM Team, and the Coordinator, so as to help these bodies to fulfil their obligations.

Beneficiaries shall promptly notify the Coordinator and the PM Team through the appropriate WPL of any significant problem or delay likely to affect the success of the project.

To summarise, each Beneficiary must:

- Do the work assigned to it in the Description of Action, and any other detailed work plan derived from it, on time, on budget, and with an appropriate level of quality.
- Collaborate with all other Beneficiaries as required by the tasks, including contributing to relevant deliverables.
- Not hinder the work of others or delay it unnecessarily.
- Attend meetings and teleconferences as required.
- Notify promptly the relevant governance body of any potential issue affecting performance. The normal chain of reporting would be, in this order: WPL → PM → MB.
- Notify the PM Team about any risk that may be detected in the course of the work, and that may affect future performance.
- Fulfil the administrative and financial reporting obligations according to EC rules.
- Spend the costs foreseen only for the work expected in CONVERGE, and report it faithfully.

6. KEY LEGAL DOCUMENTS

6.1. The Grant Agreement

The Grant Agreement (GA) is the main legal document underpinning the project's execution – effectively, a contract between the beneficiaries and the EC. It is first signed by the EC and the Coordinator. Each beneficiary then accedes to the Grant Agreement by executing an accession form. The Grant Agreement mainly provides information on the grant (parties, duration, start date, budget, etc.), obligations of the Beneficiaries towards the EC (such as reporting requirements), as well as the intellectual property framework and other legal conditions. The Grant Agreement is dated 1st February 2020 and has the GA # 871075.

The Grant Agreement core document includes a standard text (i.e. it is essentially the same for any EC Horizon 2020 project) describing the general rules and regulations governing EC projects, including financial rules (e.g. which costs are acceptable, how payments are handled, etc.), Intellectual Property Rights (who owns the results, how access to such results is enabled, etc.) and other general conditions applicable to EC projects. These generic provisions can be supplemented (but not contravened) with project-specific provisions via a Consortium Agreement (see below), which enables projects to set out their specific IPR detailed rules, governance mechanisms, etc.

Beyond its core terms and conditions, mostly standard text, the Grant Agreement also includes the following annexes, which form an integral part of the contract:

6.1.1. Annex 1. Description of the action (DoA)

The most extensive and important Annex to the Grant Agreement is the Description of Action (DoA), which comprises the technical description of the work to be undertaken in the project (work packages, tasks, deliverables, milestones), the description and roles of the different partners, allocated effort in person-months, and budget details. The DoA is derived from the original proposal submitted to the EC for evaluation and approval, and it is the benchmark against which project progress will be judged. Compared to the rest of the Grant Agreement and annexes, which are mostly model texts, the DoA is specific for each project. It is important to remember that the DoA is an integral part of the Grant Agreement, and therefore it is a contractual commitment of all beneficiaries.

6.1.2. Annex 2. Estimated Budget for the action

This Annex refers to the overall budget for the CONVERGE Project and includes the budget details for all project beneficiaries. This document is automatically generated by the EC Participant Portal.

6.1.3. Annex 3. Accession form for beneficiaries

This form is required to be signed by all the project beneficiaries to formally accede to the CONVERGE Grant Agreement. If a new beneficiary joins the project, this form will be requested to be signed by the new institution joining the project.

6.1.4. Annex 4. Financial statement

This form refers to the summary of costs to be reported by those partners receiving EC funding for each reporting period. Please see section 7.3.3. (Financial Reporting) for more details.

6.1.5. Annex 5. Model for the Certificate on Financial Statements

This Annex is required for those partners that request a total EC funding of €325,000 or more, as reimbursement of actual costs calculated based on its usual cost accounting practices. Please see section 7.3.3. (Financial Reporting) for more details.

6.1.6. Annex 6. Model for the Certificate on the Methodology

Beneficiaries may submit to the EC, for approval by the Commission, a certificate on the methodology to state that their usual cost accounting practices comply with specific conditions (e.g. "unit costs" instead of actual costs). Once the certificate is approved, costs declared in line with this methodology will not be challenged subsequently, unless the beneficiaries have concealed information for the purpose of the approval.

The Grant Agreement and its Annexes are available on the CONVERGE Google Drive³⁵.

6.1.7. Changes to the Grant Agreement

The Grant Agreement can and must be changed whenever any important project parameter changes: partnership, project duration, budget, etc. Implementation of such changes must follow a specific procedure called 'Grant Agreement amendment'. Most changes that trigger Grant Agreement amendments relate to updates in the Description of Action (DoA) (e.g. changes in tasks and deliverables, changes in efforts allocated, changes in partner's teams, budget transfers across beneficiaries, etc.). These can be relatively minor, in which case they tend to be grouped and implemented together in one go, or major, which might trigger an amendment on their own, especially if it is urgent that the change is officially entered into the contract.

Grant Agreement amendments are submitted to the EC by the Coordinator on behalf of the Consortium. This implies that the Consortium must be aware of and approve any proposed changes before the amendment is requested.

The PM Team will be responsible for following-up on amendments to the Grant Agreement during the project.

The procedure is as follows:

³⁵ https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1fnSik_m6fmVA-oRIZki_Nh5H5l15F3o

1. The Project Management Team (PM Team) will keep track of all needed amendments. Meetings and communications with the beneficiaries affected will enable the PM Team to compile all the necessary information to support the changes.
2. The list of modifications will be circulated to the General Assembly for their information and approval.
3. The PM Team will prepare the following documentation:
 - A new version of the DoA with the modifications in track changes.
 - A first version of a "Request Letter" to be sent to the EC Project Officer including the changes.
 - Other documents needed to request modifications.
4. The PM Team will circulate an amended version of the DoA to the Managing Board for validation. The approval by the Managing Board will be required for any Amendment to the Grant Agreement.
5. As a final step the Coordinator, supported by the PM Team, will submit on behalf of the Consortium, the Request Letter, the new version of the DoA and all the additional documentation required by EC for the changes submitted.
6. Once approved, the new version of the DoA will also be accessible in the CONVERGE Google Drive³⁶ in the appropriate amendment folder.

The Grant Agreement may be affected by other types of minor changes which do not constitute an amendment, but which must be communicated to the consortium or to the EC through an information procedure. In any case, beneficiaries should contact the PM Team to confirm the procedure to follow for any modification needed.

For more information about the procedure, review the section 4.3. (Project Change Management).

6.2. The Consortium Agreement

The Consortium Agreement (CA) is concluded between the CONVERGE Beneficiaries in order to provide a legal framework for their collaboration within the boundaries of the Grant Agreement. The CA includes provisions on, for instance, governance, intellectual property, dissemination, and liability. The EC is not a party to the CA. The fully executed CA is accessible in the CONVERGE Google Drive³⁷.

Amendments to the CA may also be necessary in the course of the project, sometimes purely as a consequence of Grant Agreement amendments. These CA amendments will be handled separately by agreement of all beneficiaries, under the coordination of the Coordinator with the support of the PM Team.

³⁶ https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1GoVIPU5DOoWEvaU_Dd3h-WoKyOPh3xHu

³⁷ https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1xt_KfzoALIQomp2L3eQOxpffqog3ul9X

The Project Coordinator shall keep records of the Consortium Agreement together with (i) all amendments to the Grant Agreement amending the Consortium Agreement, and (ii) any other amendments to the Consortium Agreement.

7. PROJECT REPORTING

7.1. Deliverables

7.1.1. Who generates project deliverables?

As official results of the project, deliverables deserve special attention and are generated and reviewed according to specific procedures. As a general rule, the generation of deliverables is a responsibility of the corresponding work package lead beneficiary and the process will be supervised by the corresponding WPL. The lead beneficiary will be responsible for drafting the deliverable and gathering contributions from work package participants as appropriate. Prior to submission to the EC, deliverables will undergo an internal review process that is detailed below.

In order to ensure uniformity in the presentation across the project and facilitate the consolidation of contributions from different partners, the template for deliverables has been generated by the PM Team based on the official EC template, and it is available on the CONVERGE Google Drive in the Guidance and Templates folder³⁸.

When naming the document it is expected that the document naming convention is adhered to.

Example: ELIXIR-CONVERGE_Del#_Title_Version#.

(e.g. ELIXIR-CONVERGE_D5.3_Project Handbook_v1.0.pdf)

7.1.2. Deliverable structure, guidance and tips

Project deliverables are to be submitted at specific times stated in the DoA (Part A Section 1.3.2 WT2 list of deliverables³⁹).

Note: The “expected delivery date” listed in the DoA always refers to the last date of any month. e.g. ‘June 2020’ means ‘30th June 2020’ / ‘Feb 2021’ means ‘28th Feb 2021’.

Deliverables reflect the results achieved during the lifetime of the project, and they are important documents to assess the progress achieved.

Each deliverable must use the deliverable template pre-prepared by the PM Team and shared in the monthly Project Monitoring report. In addition, a clean copy of the deliverable template can be found in the Templates folder on the CONVERGE Google Drive⁴⁰.

The template has six predefined sections:

³⁸ https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1PNEtZzOKk7Gp_GH84KYcgUr4yMqInG8T

³⁹ https://drive.google.com/open?id=1B8TPadY56WIOY_qrysnLvceKcqnllaJO

⁴⁰ <https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1cxSNL4oxRVw-dsLPUI7p6QpIKdifD8GR>

- Executive Summary (Max ½ page, should provide an overview of the work carried out and the conclusion)
- Contribution Towards Project Objectives (indicate with Yes/No if the deliverable contributes to the key result)
- Introduction (1-1 ½ pages, describe deliverable scope and the methodology to be applied)
- Description of Work Accomplished (Describe what has been done. Interactions with other WPs? Collaboration with external partners/projects? Dissemination activities carried out?)
- Results (Present and discuss the results obtained)
- Conclusion
- Impact (Present and discuss the impact obtained)
- Next Steps
- Deviation from Description of Action (If applicable, describe the deviation from the Description of Action and the justification and plans to avoid this deviation impacting the work plan)

7.1.3. Deliverable review process

7.1.3.1. Review for quality

The review process must use the following quality criteria as reference.

As regards to content:

- **Completeness:** Information must address all aspects related to the purpose for which the information is produced. On the other hand, redundancy of information must be avoided, as it obscures the clarity of documents.

Related indicators: Missing content, Redundancy.

- **Accuracy:** Information contained in the document must be reliable and must correspond with reality. This means that all background information used in the reports should be appropriately supported by references. Foreground information should be sufficiently supported so that misinterpretation is avoided. Use of statistically validated objective data is to be prioritised.

Related indicators: Error, Insufficient references/objective supporting data, Ambiguity.

- **Relevance:** Information used in the document should be focused on the key issues and be written in a fashion that takes into consideration its target audience.

Related indicators: Irrelevant information.

- **Depth:** all information used should be provided to the depth needed for the purpose of the document.

Related indicators: Lacking detail, Excessive detail.

As regards to appearance and structure:

- Adherence to standards: it is important that deliverables are prepared with uniform appearance and structure so that, even if they are produced by different authors, they appear as originating from a single initiative.

Related indicators: Lack of uniformity in presentation.

7.1.3.2. The review process

Within the CONVERGE project, the review process shall be coordinated by the PM Team.

As and when a deliverable approaches due, it will appear in the monthly project monitoring report three months prior to submission deadline. A link to the deliverable template will be provided, as well as guidelines for producing the document.

If the WPL themselves will not be drafting the deliverable, it is their responsibility to forward the request to the appropriate team member(s) who will be undertaking the task of drafting the deliverable (the deliverable authors).

The Deliverable Lead must nominate a minimum of two reviewers. Before informing the PM Team of who the reviewers will be they should seek agreement from the nominated reviewers. The reviewers should ideally be from a different WP and have a thorough understanding of the deliverable topic so they can provide sufficient technical critique/review. If it is deemed that the review by someone with additional expertise is required, e.g. such as a case where a deliverable has a focus on ethical or regulatory/legal issues, members of any of the Advisory Boards of the CONVERGE project may also be asked to be a reviewer.

The deliverable author(s) should work on their deliverable within their Work Package folder on the CONVERGE Google Drive.

Where more than one person is producing the deliverable, the lead deliverable author should create a Table of Contents and assign responsibilities to the other authors.

If the WPL(s) do not draft the report themselves, once the first draft of the document is produced by the author(s), they will be expected to have the WPLs review it to assess the content from a scientific/technical perspective.

Reviewers will be expected to check the deliverable against the quality criteria described in section 4.1.3.1. above. Any suggested edits or comments should be made within the Google Doc which allows for a collaborative working environment. The deliverable author(s), must then proceed with the amendments or comments on the reviewed document.

1.5 weeks prior to the deliverable due date, the final draft of the document should be submitted to the PM Team, by emailing them a link to the Google Doc version on the CONVERGE Google Drive. PM will distribute the link to the MB for a final review, allowing the MB seven (7) days to review it. Once approved, the PM Team (on behalf of the Project Coordinator) will convert the Google Doc to PDF and submit the final document to the EC via the Participant Portal. In addition, the PM Team will upload all public deliverable reports to Zenodo (see also Section 4.6.6, Open Access policy and requirements) and notify the Consortium. The final document will also be available on the CONVERGE Google Drive in the Deliverables and Milestones folder⁴¹.

During the whole process, it is recommended that there is one responsible author that acts on behalf of all authors and communicates with them for evolving the document.

7.1.3.3. Illustrative timelines

1. **Three months** prior to the due date, the deliverable will appear in the monthly project monitoring report with a link to the pre-prepared deliverable template.
2. **Two months (60 days)** prior to the due date, author(s) identify the reviewers and inform PM.
3. If multiple people will be producing the deliverable, the lead author should create a Table of Contents and assign responsibilities to the other authors.
4. Author(s) produce the first draft of the deliverable report.
5. If the author(s) are not the WPLs, they must have the WPLs review the deliverable report.
6. **1 month (30 days)** prior to the due date, author(s) must send the draft report to PM Team by emailing them a link to the Google Doc version on the CONVERGE Google Drive. The PM Team will review the draft for formatting before forwarding it to the pre-identified reviewers, allowing them two weeks to provide comments directly within the Google Doc.
7. Reviewers' input is gathered within the Google Doc using suggested edits and comments.
8. Author(s) generate a revised version of the document taking on board the suggestions and comments of the reviewers.
9. **1.5 weeks (10 days)** prior to the due date, author(s) must send the final version to the PM Team by emailing them a link to the Google Doc version on the CONVERGE Google Drive. PM Team will then circulate the document (via emailed link) to the MB (all WPLs) for final review, allowing them seven (7) days to review the document. The MB are encouraged to make any suggestions or comments directly within the Google Doc.
10. **Three days** prior to the due date, the author(s) provide the PM Team with the consolidated, final version.
11. The Coordinator (or the PM Team on their behalf) will convert the Google Doc to PDF and upload the final version in the Participant Portal and to Zenodo.
12. The final version of the document is also uploaded to the 'Submitted' folder within the respective reporting period subfolder (e.g. RP₁, RP₂, RP₃) in the 04. Deliverables and Milestones folder⁴² on the CONVERGE Google Drive.
04. Deliverables and Milestones → RP₁ → Submitted

⁴¹ <https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1i8WQ7BR6fAObvDJg4Mji8MNq7t53oQxg>

⁴² <https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1i8WQ7BR6fAObvDJg4Mji8MNq7t53oQxg>

Note: Although the illustrative timeline starts three months prior to due date with drafting beginning two month prior to the due date, this process can begin earlier if the authors wish, and deliverables can be submitted ahead of schedule.

In case of time constraints, an exceptional streamlined procedure for the deliverables may apply upon agreement with the MB.

A tracker with the deliverable due dates is available on the CONVERGE Google Drive⁴³.

7.2. Milestones

Each milestone must use a clean copy of the milestone template⁴⁴ and must not exceed one slide.

It is the responsibility of the Milestone Lead organisation⁴⁵ to produce the milestone report or to deputise the responsibility to someone else upon their agreement.

7.2.1. Illustrative timelines

1. **3 months** prior to the due date, the milestone will appear in the monthly project monitoring report with a link to the pre-prepared milestone template
2. **1.5 months (45 days)** prior to the due date, if the author(s) are not the WPLs, they must have the WPLs review the milestone before submitting it.
3. **1.5 weeks (10 days)** prior to the due date, author(s) must send the final version to the PM Team by emailing them a link to the Google Doc version on the CONVERGE Google Drive. PM will then circulate the document (via emailed link) to the MB (all WPLs) for final review, allowing them seven (7) days to provide any comment. The MB are encouraged to make any suggestions or comments directly within the Google Doc however, this shouldn't be a time consuming process for the MB.
4. **Three days** prior to the due date, the author(s) provide the PM Team with the final version.
5. The Coordinator (or the PM Team on their behalf) will convert the Google Doc to PDF and upload it in Participant Portal.
6. The final version of the document is also uploaded to the 'Submitted' folder within the respective reporting period subfolder (e.g. RP₁, RP₂, RP₃) in the o4. Deliverables and Milestones folder⁴⁶ on the CONVERGE Google Drive.

A tracker with the milestone due dates is available on the CONVERGE Google Drive⁴⁷.

⁴³ <https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1abzvq03sLsF1e007tGIYgsybAagyJAQInSvociU--fk/edit#gid=1091470126>

⁴⁴ https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1cVxZtW5UyunJP4ISPzrv4p_7qc7CRsur

⁴⁵ <https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1abzvq03sLsF1e007tGIYgsybAagyJAQInSvociU--fk/edit#gid=1091470126>

⁴⁶ https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1RwHcsPXTaXKhIMtnaYbuzTVRIT1_8Jo6

⁴⁷ <https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1abzvq03sLsF1e007tGIYgsybAagyJAQInSvociU--fk/edit#gid=1091470126>

7.3. Progress reporting

7.3.1. EC Project Periodic Technical Reports

Throughout the entire project execution period (1st February 2020 until 31st January 2023), the Consortium is required to submit, in due time, three periodic technical reports to the EC using the template periodic report⁴⁸ provided in the EC Participant Portal⁴⁹. The project is officially divided into 2 periods for both progress and financial reporting to the EC:

- RP1: 1st Feb 2020 to 31st July 2021 (M1-18)
- RP2: 1st August 2021 to 31st July 2023 (M19-42)

In compliance with the rules specified in Clause 20.3 of the CONVERGE Grant Agreement (Periodic reports – Request for interim payments)⁵⁰, periodic reports have to be submitted to the EC within 60 days after the end of each reporting period.

The periodic technical report must include the following:

- an explanation of the work carried out by the beneficiaries;
- an overview of the progress towards the objectives of the action, including milestones and deliverables identified in Annex 1;
 - an explanation justifying any differences between work expected to be carried out in accordance with Annex 1 and that actually carried out;
 - an overview of the exploitation and dissemination of the results and, if required in Annex 1, an updated 'plan for the exploitation and dissemination of the results'.
 - an overview of the communication activities;
- a summary for publication by the EC;
- the answers to the 'questionnaire', covering issues related to the action implementation and the economic and societal impact, notably in the context of the EC and the Horizon 2020 key performance indicators and EC and the Horizon 2020 monitoring requirements.

Each partner shall send or provide within the technical report template, as requested, information about the work performed and efforts devoted in the corresponding period to the PM Team, within 30 calendar days after the end of the reporting period. Effort figures can however be requested by the PM Team at any point during the project. For the purpose of accountability, beneficiaries are requested to keep track of their efforts at the task/activity level. This facilitates the linkage between effort and progress when reporting to the EC.

⁴⁸ https://drive.google.com/open?id=1silKGlyW_wzvHQUJn-TweWoX3MCtEcBE

⁴⁹

https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/docs/h2020-funding-guide/grants/grant-management/reports/periodic-reports_en.htm#partB

⁵⁰ <https://drive.google.com/open?id=1gLhclTzFumCGuobTsZBPcZKFcPB2m5Qn>

The Periodic Technical Report template provided by the EC can be found on the CONVERGE Google Drive⁵¹. This template will be used for each of the two Periodic Technical Reports unless the EC produces an amended version throughout the course of the CONVERGE project.

Detailed instructions on the submission of the periodic technical report will be provided by the PM Team to all partners in advance of the reporting deadline.

7.3.2. Financial Reporting

Disclaimer: Beneficiaries must always ensure they follow the EC financial reporting guidelines. The details provided here are valid at the date of the document submission but may be superseded by changes to EC rules. See the Financial Reporting Guidelines available on the EC Participant Portal⁵² for further information.

As with all EC Horizon 2020 projects, each CONVERGE project beneficiary has a budget, which comprises the estimated costs that will be incurred during the project lifecycle. These costs can be covered with EC funding. Total funding received by a beneficiary cannot exceed its costs (i.e. it cannot yield a profit derived from participation in the project).

EC funding follows EC reimbursement rules, which imply in the CONVERGE project a maximum 100% of the costs reimbursed for eligible project activities. EC funding is paid in several instalments: an advance payment (pre-financing) at the beginning of the project, periodic interim payments reimbursing the costs reported and accepted in each Periodic Report (up to a total amount of 85% of the total funding for a beneficiary), and a final payment of the remaining 15% of the total funding.

Budgeted efforts and costs are available in the DoA. When agreed by the MB, budgets can be adjusted by transfers of amounts between beneficiaries or between budget categories (or both) during the project life. This may not require an amendment, if the action is implemented as described in DoA. In case of subcontracting, these costs should be included in the DoA (via Amendment if needed) to make sure they are accepted by the EC as costs claimed.

7.3.2.1. Eligible costs

Costs which are categorised as eligible may be claimed for reimbursement. In order to consider project costs as eligible and therefore be approved by the EC, they must fulfil the following general conditions:

- They must be actually incurred by the beneficiary;
- They must be incurred in connection with the action as described in the DoA and necessary for its implementation;
- They must be determined in accordance with the usual accounting principles of the beneficiary;

⁵¹ https://drive.google.com/open?id=1silKGlyW_wzvHQUJn-TweWoX3MCtEcBE

⁵² https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/docs/h2020-funding-guide/grants/grant-management/reports/periodic-reports_en.htm#partB

- They must be incurred during the duration of the project, with the exception of costs relating to the submission of the periodic report for the last reporting period and the final report;
- They must be recorded in the beneficiaries' accounts;
- They must comply with the applicable national law on taxes, and social security;
- They must be reasonable, justified and must comply with the principle of sound financial management, in particular regarding economy and efficiency;
- They must be indicated in the estimated overall budget in the DoA.

Beneficiaries should take into account, in the day-to-day administration of the project, some practical advice that may facilitate their financial management.

Beneficiaries need to:

- be aware of their own budget distribution;
- coordinate their financial flows: budget, funding, expenditure, justification, payments;
- avoid inconsistencies between efforts spent in the project (recorded in time sheets) and personnel cost justification.

'Budget' refers to costs that each partner is expected to incur, as declared in the DoA. The amount contributed by the EC is called 'funding' or 'EC contribution', and corresponds to 100% of the eligible costs. A beneficiary has to justify its total budget in order to get the expected funding in full. The actual costs incurred during the project (the 'practical' implementation of the planned budget) is called the 'expenditure'. These costs will conform to EC rules and therefore be justifiable. Lastly, 'payments' refer to the actual amounts transferred to the partners' accounts during the project. These depend on the funding of each partner and the justification accepted by the EC, and cannot exceed the total funding of each beneficiary.

Identification of eligible costs:

Personnel Costs. The EC follows a policy of full cost justification for all beneficiaries. This means that the hours devoted by all of the personnel involved in a project can be justified, irrespective of them being newly hired for the project or permanent staff.

For the justification of personnel costs in the periodic financial statement, beneficiaries must take into account the efforts (expressed in person-months) reported for the same period so that these are consistent with the amounts justified. Personnel costs are understood to include salaries, social charges, etc.; all of the actual costs that the person represents for the institution.

The personnel costs are normally calculated by the hourly rate multiplied by the number of actual hours worked for the project.

The hourly rate (based on actual costs) can be calculated as: actual annual personnel costs, divided by the number of annual productive hours. The number of annual productive hours that makes a person-month can vary between partners. All partners must calculate their specific

productive hours according to the internal accounting practice for their organisation. In case different categories of personnel have different working conditions, individual productive hours may be calculated. The productive hours per year should exclude annual leave, public holidays, training (if not project related) and sick leave.

In addition, for personnel costs, the beneficiaries must keep time records for the number of hours declared for all actual work performed for the project. The time records must be in writing and approved by the persons working for the action and their supervisors, at least monthly.

It is advised that time records should include:

- the title and Grant Agreement number of the project, as specified in the GA;
- the beneficiary's full name, as specified in the GA;
- the full name, date and signature of the person working for the action;
- the number of hours worked for the action in the period covered by the time record; it is highly recommended that the number of hours is detailed per day (hours worked for the action in each day);
- short description of the work carried out during the month;
- the supervisor's full name and signature.

According to Article 18.1.2 of the Grant Agreement: "as an exception, for persons working exclusively on the action, there is no need to keep time records, if the participant signs a declaration confirming that the persons have worked exclusively on the action". Nonetheless, institution rules need to be consulted first.

Other direct costs

Travel and subsistence costs

- As a general rule, common meetings expenses (catering, meeting rooms, etc.) shall be paid and justified by the host partner/s in the corresponding reporting period under the "other direct costs" category.
- Travel costs must be needed for the work in the project, or for activities related to it (e.g. presentation of a paper explaining the results of the project in a conference). Travel costs related to a conference where no specific project-related work will be performed or presented by the beneficiary would not be eligible. Travel costs should be limited to the necessity for the project; any extension of the travel for other professional or private reasons is not an eligible cost.
- Each partner must apply the travel rules of their own organisation (i.e. some organisations reimburse a flat rate allowance for meal expenses while others reimburse actual costs).

The ELIXIR Hub provide decision trees for determining who pays for travel and meeting costs - the hosting organisation or the beneficiary:

Who pays what? **Event organiser** or **external source**?

Venue costs:

Figure 6. Venue costs decision tree

Travel costs:

Figure 7. Travel costs decision tree

For more information, see ELIXIR’s Guidelines and Tips for Events - for event organisers⁵³.

The depreciation costs of equipment, infrastructure or other assets (new or second hand) as recorded in the beneficiary’s accounts are eligible, if they are purchased and written off in

⁵³ https://docs.google.com/document/d/12YrPswEuUywsRaYdjUDjaq-bvhm_e_gOqd1pM44vmc/edit#

accordance with the beneficiary’s usual accounting principles. The only portion of the costs that will be taken into account is that which corresponds to the duration of the action and the rate of actual use for the purpose of the action.

Costs of other goods and services (consumables, supplies, dissemination, protection of results, certificates on the financial statements, certificates on the methodology, translations, publications) are eligible if they are purchased specifically for the project.

Subcontracting and other third parties’ costs. Regarding subcontracting costs, it is paramount that the DoA includes a specification that enables approval by the EC.

The EC lay a ground rule that all partners must have the technical and financial resources needed to carry out the project themselves, but if it is necessary to implement the project, a beneficiary may call upon subcontractors to implement “action tasks” described in Article 13.1 of the Grant Agreement (“Subcontracting”)⁵⁴.

Indirect costs. Indirect costs or overheads (e.g. heating, lighting, security, office supplies, etc.), which represents a fair apportionment of the overall overheads of the institution, are to be added to the above-mentioned categories. As they are indirect, these costs are not justified using invoices, etc., but are simply stated in the financial statement as a 25% flat rate of the direct costs (except for subcontracting and the costs of resources made available by third parties which are not used on the premises of the beneficiary, which bear no overheads).

⁵⁴ <https://drive.google.com/open?id=1gLhclTzFumCGuobTsZBPcZKFcPB2m5Qn>

Figure 8. An overview of how to determine a subcontractor, linked third party, third party providing in-kind contributions or in-house consultant.

If in doubt, we encourage you to email converge-pm@elixir-europe.org for further guidance or clarification.

7.3.2.2. Non-Eligible costs.

Non-Eligible costs: costs which can not be claimed.

The EC state that there are some costs which cannot be considered eligible and therefore, can not be included in the financial statement:

Costs that do not comply with the conditions set out in Articles 6.1 to 6.4 of the Grant Agreement, in particular:

- Costs related to return on capital
 - Debt and service debt charges
 - Provisions for possible future losses or charges
 - Interest owed
 - Doubtful debts
 - Currency exchange losses
 - Bank costs charged by the beneficiary's bank for transfers from the Commission
 - Excessive or reckless expenditure
 - Deductible VAT
 - Costs incurred during suspension of the implementation of the action.
-
- Any costs which do not meet the conditions established in the previous section.

Costs declared under another EU or Euratom grant (including grants awarded by a Member State and financed by the EU or Euratom budget and grants awarded by bodies other than the Commission for the purpose of implementing the EU or Euratom budget); in particular, indirect costs if the beneficiary is already receiving an operating grant financed by the EU or Euratom budget in the same period, unless it can demonstrate that the operating grant does not cover any costs of the action.

7.3.2.3. Submitting the financial statement

The financial statement is an official statement submitted by the beneficiary. Any Linked Third Parties (LTP) must provide their financial statement to the project beneficiary who in turn, must submit the report to the EC on their behalf. In the financial statement the beneficiary must declare any costs incurred during the specific reporting period for which they wish to be reimbursed by the EC, where applicable.

The EC uses an online application tool called the Funding & Tenders Opportunities Portal for the submission of financial statements. Each beneficiary has access to the portal and are expected to submit their costs there. A sample Financial Statement is available in the Portal⁵⁵.

Cost must be filled in the Funding & Tender Opportunities Portal within 20 calendar days after the end of the reporting period together with the explanation of use of resources. It is advised that beneficiaries prepare in advance for reporting and liaise with any relevant financial or administrative department in their respective institution at least one month in advance of the end of the reporting period.

Specific guidelines for accessing the Participant Portal will also be provided by the PM Team in the months leading up to the reporting period. These guidelines will include complete instructions and recommendations for adequate reporting.

7.3.2.4. Adjustments to previous periods

Any adjustment (retroactive modification of costs submitted in previous periods) requires the submission of a supplementary Financial statement for the period, where the details of that adjustment will appear.

Together with the new financial statement, the details and justification for the adjustment must be provided by the participant in the periodic report.

Therefore, for correction of financial statements submitted in previous reporting periods, the following need to be submitted:

- One Financial statement for the current period;
- One separate Financial statement for every previous period where adjustments are needed, which will include those adjusted (negative/positive) costs of that specific previous period.

If these costs need to be covered by a Certificate on Financial Statements (CFS), they could be supported within the CFS for the current period but with a specific indication by the auditor certifying both the supplementary costs incurred in previous periods and those claimed in the current one.

7.3.3. Final Report

Within 60 days after the end of the project, and in addition to the periodic report for the last reporting period, the Consortium must also submit a final report to the EC. This final report must include the following:

1. A 'final technical report' with a summary for publication containing:
 - a. an overview of the results and their exploitation and dissemination;

⁵⁵ https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/gm/reporting/h2020-tmpl-periodic-rep_en.pdf#page=23

- b. the conclusions on the action, and;
 - c. the socio-economic impact of the action.
2. A 'final financial report' containing:
- a. a 'final summary financial statement', created automatically by the electronic exchange system, consolidating the individual financial statements for all reporting periods and including the request for payment of the balance and;
 - b. a 'certificate on the financial statements' for each beneficiary, if it requests a total contribution of €325,000 or more, as reimbursement of actual costs and unit costs calculated on the basis of its usual cost accounting practices.

This final report will be prepared by the PM Team and the MB with input from all WPs.

The PM Team will also coordinate the elaboration of the final financial report that accompanies the technical report and in which reported figures from all participants throughout the project are consolidated.

Detailed instructions on the submission of the final report will be provided by the PM Team to all partners in advance of the reporting deadline.

7.3.4. Certificate on the Financial Statement (CFS)

A certificate on the financial statement (CFS), also named audit certificate, is a statement from a competent auditor in which correctness and compliance with EC rules of a cost justification is certified.

A CFS must be submitted together with the corresponding financial cost statement at the end of the project by all beneficiaries if the beneficiary requests a total contribution of 325,000 Euro or more, as reimbursement of actual costs and unit costs calculated on the basis of its usual cost accounting practices.

Auditors eligible to deliver audit certificates must be "external auditors" or "public competent officers" who are "independent" and "qualified to carry out statutory audits of accounting documents". It is highly recommended to determine an adequate auditor well before the end of the reporting period to ensure his/her availability for a timely generation of the audit certificate.

As a guideline, Annex 5 of the Grant Agreement includes the terms of reference and independent report of factual findings for the certificate of financial statements.

7.3.5. EC Funding

The EC funding is paid to the Coordinator (ELIXIR Hub), who distributes it to the beneficiaries without unjustified delay.

Some general rules apply with respect to the payments:

- The EC paid a pre-financing amount at the start of the project which was distributed to the beneficiaries receiving funding;

- Interim payments will be depending on costs justified and accepted after each reporting period, and distributed after receipt from the EC;
- A final payment will be released by the EC corresponding to the costs accepted for the last reporting period, plus any adjustment needed.

Total payments during the project cannot exceed 85% of the total funding. 15% of the funding will only be paid after final reports are approved.

The most important notion for beneficiaries to bear in mind is that payments follow costs reported – and costs reported follow work done for the project. The Coordinator has the right to reject costs reported by any beneficiary if they are not in line with the work performed.

7.3.6. Receipts of the project

The receipts (in lay terms, 'income received due to the project') of the project are:

- Resources **made available by third parties to the partner** by means of financial transfers or contributions in-kind which are free of charge:
 - Shall be considered a receipt of the project if they have been contributed by the third party specifically to be used on the project.
 - Shall not be considered a receipt of the project if their use is at the discretion of the participant's management.
- **Income generated by the project:**
 - Shall be considered a receipt for the participant when generated by actions undertaken in carrying out the project and from the sale of assets purchased under the grant agreement up to the value of the cost initially charged to the project by the participant;
 - Shall not be considered a receipt for the participant when generated from the research use or direct exploitation of foreground resulting from the project.

7.4. Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)

The outcomes and impact of the project in relation to the call text will be assessed against Key Performance Indicators (See table 17). Relating to all WPs, these KPIs can easily be monitored, from the project onset and will be refined in Task 5.3. Progress against these KPIs must be reported to the governance boards, to inform project planning and management, looking forwards (rather than post-hoc assessment), ensuring corrective actions are taken as and when they are needed. Some of these indicators already form part of ELIXIR's suite of indicators, which are used to monitor the infrastructure's performance (mostly internally-facing) and impact (mostly externally-facing), in line with ESFRI's current work on ensuring that the infrastructures it has recognised are adequately monitored.

A full list of the KPIs as identified in the Description of Action Part B⁵⁶ can be viewed in the table below:

Table 17. CONVERGE KPIs.

<p>Expected Impact (Call text) and ELIXIR-CONVERGE approach to deliver and go beyond</p>
<p>Contribute to providing Europe with a comprehensive landscape of sustainable Research Infrastructures helping to respond to challenges in science, industry and society;</p>
<p>ELIXIR-CONVERGE will enhance the sustainability of existing and well-established research infrastructure services, a number of which are already recommended for use by funders (e.g. the ELIXIR Deposition Databases). These services increase research efficiency and enable data-driven applications and innovation (in academia and industry) in the fields of health, food security and the environment. The project will also contribute to building capacity in terms of data management/data stewardship, at the pan-European scale - this, along with the data management toolkit, will unlock the routine adoption of FAIR principles in the life sciences, thereby increasing the amount and quality of data made available to researchers in academia and industry.</p> <p>ELIXIR-CONVERGE will work to empower ELIXIR Nodes in evaluating and communicating their performance and impact to important stakeholders in the policy sphere, including funders of research infrastructures. Based on an increased appreciation of needs and expectations of funders, ELIXIR Nodes will be able to sustain the research infrastructures that underpin responses to societal and socioeconomic challenges [refined March 2021]</p> <p>Planned Key Performance Indicators:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Number of ELIXIR supported projects taking steps to implement data management best practices and associated toolkit - Number of ELIXIR Nodes developing business models for the provision of data management support [proposed June 2021]
<p>Strengthen the European Research Area position and role in the global research environment;</p>
<p>ELIXIR-CONVERGE will influence relevant stakeholders and drive the adoption of data management good practices and tools, in Europe and beyond, thereby increasing the impact of European-funded research [refined March 2021]</p> <p>Planned Key Performance Indicators:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Number of consultation responses and actions to increase European and international visibility of key ELIXIR-CONVERGE outputs with key stakeholders and the policy sphere more broadly [new March 2021]

⁵⁶ <https://drive.google.com/open?id=1K66wz0jDS3K6VypdzyV67PgAIMPpKduW>

Reinforce the partnership between the Commission, Member States, Associated Countries and relevant stakeholders in establishing pan-European research infrastructures;

ELIXIR-CONVERGE will run events in, and organise meetings with, prospective ELIXIR Member countries, so as to raise awareness of ELIXIR and its services
[refined March 2021]

Planned Key Performance Indicators:

- Number of events/meetings targeting prospective ELIXIR Member countries
[new March 2021]

Enhance the role of the Union in international organisations and multilateral fora;

ELIXIR-CONVERGE will showcase research infrastructure outputs/achievements that have been funded by the European Union
[new March 2021]

Planned Key Performance Indicators:

- Mentions of ELIXIR-CONVERGE and its key outputs in European and international policy documents
[new March 2021]

Support progress towards the development of global research infrastructures;

ELIXIR-CONVERGE will share the new knowledge generated during the project in peer-reviewed journals, for the benefit of other research infrastructures around the globe
[new March 2021]

ELIXIR-CONVERGE will work to mobilise global-scale COVID-19 related data and make them freely available for reuse by researchers from the public and private sectors
[new March 2021]

Planned Key Performance Indicators:

- Number of publications (peer-reviewed and preprints) acknowledging ELIXIR-CONVERGE and/or presenting its achievements
[new March 2021]
- Number of records available from the COVID-19 Data Portal
[new March 2021]
- Number of operational national-level COVID-19 Data Portals [new June 2021]

- Number of contributors, describing [number of] tools/resources on [number of] individual guidance pages on data management. Number of individual visitors from [number of] countries [proposed July 2021]

Enable researchers to address societal challenges with a global dimension;

ELIXIR-CONVERGE will showcase the benefits and scalability of data management through a set of (five) pan-European demonstrator projects, in different thematic and impact areas of relevance to the Sustainable Development Goals.

Planned Key Performance Indicators:

- Demonstrator projects successfully implementing data management best practices, as tracked via specific metrics

Foster capacity-building and Research Infrastructure human capital development in targeted/relevant regions.

ELIXIR-CONVERGE will contribute to increasing human capital at the European-scale, notably by filling in an acute gap in data management skills and expertise, including in prospective ELIXIR Member countries (e.g. in EU-13).

ELIXIR-CONVERGE will support the development of research infrastructure personnel in data management. This will be done through the creation and operation of an ELIXIR Data Management Network bringing together the data management community across ELIXIR, and fostering the exchange of knowledge on this topic and the delivery of scientific best practice [new March 2021]

Planned Key Performance Indicators:

- Number of training related activities, including in prospective ELIXIR Member countries
- Number of ELIXIR Nodes engaged in the Data Management Network [new March 2021]

In addition, Communications KPIs are detailed in ELIXIR Communications Strategy⁵⁷.

During the monthly Managing Board (WPLs) Meetings the KPI should be reviewed and updated as part of the rolling agenda.

The KPIs must be formally reviewed and updated as part of:

- M6.2 Project KPIs presented to MB - Month 12
- D6.3 Project Handbook V2 - Month 16

⁵⁷ <https://elixir-europe.org/documents/elixir-communications-strategy>

- M6.3 Project KPIs presented to MB - Month 24
- D6.4 Project Handbook final version - Month 34
- M6.4 Final project KPIs available and presented to EC as part of final report to EC - Month 36

As and when new metrics are available, it is the responsibility of the WPLs to inform the PM Team who will then include them in the dashboard to be monitored monthly.

8. DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN

The Data Management Plan (DMP) will be defined and updated throughout the project lifecycle as part of Task 6.3. The initial version of the DMP must be created by the ELIXIR Hub in the first six months of the project within WP6 (D6.2) according to the project scope and the EC requirements. It must build on the extensive DM experience in ELIXIR Nodes and so put particular attention on how the project will apply and improve existing methodologies and standards for the best practices (WP1) and common toolkit (WP3). The DMP must also provide a strategy for preservation, dissemination and sustainability of the project results. It is important to note that this project will not create additional data sets, but rather define criteria, procedures, standards and metrics. The DMP must set out the long-term access for these documents and, importantly, define ownership and plans for updating. The project does not anticipate access to research data as it will be managed by the demonstrator projects only, while the project will provide technical support on the definition and implementation of the DMP using ELIXIR resources and services.

Any questions regarding the DMP should be directed to the ELIXIR Hub (juan.arenas@elixir-europe.org).

9. ETHICAL CONSIDERATIONS

We expect ELIXIR-CONVERGE to increase the secondary use of previously collected personal data where the consent allows this and/or where the legal and ethical compliance can be ensured. Normally, the staff employed in this project will not act as the 'Data Controller/Processor', they will operate as technical experts advising the data processor on the demonstrator projects how to use ELIXIR guidance and tools to increase the FAIRness of their data. This advice will cover guidance and tools that can be used for the protection of sensitive human data as required by the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) as well as good ethical practice in research. It is a major aim of the project to allow FAIR sharing of such sensitive data in compliance with ethics and data protection law and therefore extend ELIXIR activities more towards translational medicine. WP5 have selected the demonstrator projects incorporated in the proposal and will ensure that expectations are fully accomplished by interacting with demonstrator projects and the Expert Network (WP1). In WP1 the Expert Network will advise and guide the demonstrator projects in the utilisation of ELIXIR guidance, methods, training and toolkits for their particular domain. WP2 will develop the specific training for demonstrator projects, members of the Expert Network and

ELIXIR Nodes to apply ELIXIR DMP guidelines, methods, processes and tools in their domains and in the different scenarios (support to individual researchers, Transnational Projects and International initiatives), with the main focus being the pan-european transnational projects. WP3 will define the common data management toolkit that will provide the guidance on how to implement a DMP as well as concrete realisation of the common data management toolkit for the demonstrator projects, tailoring it for the specific scientific domain, data sensitivity (as in Human Data), and scope (Local, European, International). WP4 will ensure that all the project outputs, as well as the success stories generated by the demonstrator projects, are accessible across ELIXIR and beyond (funders, policy makers, prospective ELIXIR Member States), promoting long term sustainability of the ELIXIR Nodes and evaluation the different Business Models that come out of this project. WP6 will coordinate the project's activities and apply Project Management best practices during the project execution to ensure all benefits are delivered.

Finally, ELSI expertise is ensured via the ELIXIR Node expert in this area as well as via the ELIXIR SAB.

WP6 will deliver a DMP (D6.2), in collaboration with WPs 1, 3 and 5, to provide further evidence of appropriate ethics committees and competent authorities. ELIXIR SAB includes ethics experts who will be consulted on this specific deliverable.

As ELIXIR-CONVERGE does not handle private data or highly sensitive data, most of the requirements that will apply to projects dealing with research or secondary use data are not relevant here. However, the CONVERGE project will undergo continual Ethics reviews as needed throughout the project and at a minimum, in line with the periodic reporting schedule following EC Horizon 2020 guidelines.

For more information regarding ethics within the CONVERGE project, see:

- P156 of the Description of Action, Part B, Section 5.1 Ethics⁵⁸
- P157 of the Description of Action, Part B, Section 5.1.1. EthSR Response⁵⁹

9.1. Equal Opportunities

In accordance with Article 33 - Gender Equality, of the Grant Agreement⁶⁰, beneficiaries have an obligation to aim for gender equality and must take all measures to promote equal opportunities between men and women in the implementation of the action. They must aim, to the extent possible, for a gender balance at all levels of personnel assigned to the action, including at supervisory and managerial level.

It is acknowledged by CONVERGE project partners that equal opportunities include: gender balance in research teams; gender balance in decision-making; and integrating gender/sex analysis in R&I content. The consortium is also aware of the well-known underrepresentation of women in higher-level positions in the academic sciences. A key action to address underrepresentation is to ensure that women and other underrepresented groups have equal opportunities to lead ad-hoc project working groups and present the outcome of project activities

⁵⁸ <https://drive.google.com/open?id=1K66wz0jDS3K6VypdzyV67PgAIMPpKduW>

⁵⁹ <https://drive.google.com/open?id=1K66wz0jDS3K6VypdzyV67PgAIMPpKduW>

⁶⁰ <https://drive.google.com/file/d/1gLhclTzFumCGuobTsZBPcZKFcPB2m5Qn/view>

to external stakeholders to ensure a cadre of future leaders. The PM Team and Management Board will monitor participation and representation. They will also track progress on the implementation of ELIXIR's equal opportunities strategy, notably as part of the project monitoring activities via the ELIXIR Training - Quality and Impact Assessments metrics⁶¹. In addition, training on unconscious bias will be provided to ELIXIR senior and mid-level managers (T6.4).

Of particular relevance to the implementation of CONVERGE are the following aspects:

- Equality is taken into account in all events by providing statistics and adopting action plans (e.g. speaker balance, training opportunities) as set out by the Equal Opportunities Strategy⁶² and ELIXIR Handbook of Operations⁶³ (e.g. guidelines on workshop organisation).
- The ELIXIR Hub Code of Conduct⁶⁴ is in place at all ELIXIR Hub organised and/or funded events
- To address the gender balance and help build a cadre of diverse future leaders we specifically encourage female scientists and other underrepresented groups to apply and participate in user training, workshops, and hackathons and must monitor this via KPIs to track progress (Equality KPIs are part of the formally adopted ELIXIR Training metrics)
- We are particularly aware that travel, including attending meetings and training events, is an important feature of the Expert Network and that personal situations can seriously restrict the mobility of some staff and user scientists. In this light, we must devise research and training opportunities compatible with the personal circumstances of each researcher, benefiting both female and male scientists (e.g. EMBL-EBI has successfully used avatars to provide scientists with young family remote training opportunities⁶⁵).
- The ELIXIR Equal Opportunities Strategy highlights the issue of unconscious bias in institutional procedures and recommend implementation of good practice (e.g. LIBRA handbook⁶⁶). We will provide unconscious bias training as part of management training (WP6).
- The ELIXIR Equal Opportunities strategy sets out recommendations for accessibility of online tools and services⁶⁷; ELIXIR-CONVERGE must adhere to these recommendations as part of overall attention to user experience.

For more information regarding all equal opportunity matters within the CONVERGE project, see:

- the CONVERGE Grant Agreement⁶⁸ articles listed below:
 - Article 32: Recruitment and Working Conditions for Researchers
 - Article 33: Gender Equality
 - Article 34: Ethics and Research Integrity

⁶¹ <https://docs.google.com/document/d/1BEP82K3Lg7ZpTqTU52djXIAegOcy-FNrS8hsSqKDTV4/edit#>

⁶² <https://f1000research.com/documents/7-1234>

⁶³ <https://elixir-europe.org/about-us/governance/handbook-operations>

⁶⁴ <https://elixir-europe.org/events/code-of-conduct>

⁶⁵ <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/about/news/announcements/bioinformatics-training-with-robot-avatars>

⁶⁶ <https://www.eu-libra.eu/news/libra-recruitment-handbook>

⁶⁷ E.g. by following W3C best practice: <https://www.w3.org/WAI/standards-guidelines/wcag/>

⁶⁸ <https://drive.google.com/file/d/1gLhclTzFumCGuobTsZBPcZKFcPB2m5Qn/view>

- the CONVERGE Description of Action⁶⁹:
 - Section 1.3.8 Providing Equal Opportunities to ensure diverse human capital
 - Section 3.3.1 Gender aspects and promotion of equal opportunities
- The ELIXIR Equal Opportunities Strategy⁷⁰

10. INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY RIGHTS

For all matters relating to Intellectual Property Rights please refer to:

1. Section 8 (Intellectual Property - Access Rights) of the CONVERGE Consortium Agreement⁷¹
2. Article 23a (Management of Intellectual Property) of the CONVERGE Grant Agreement⁷²

Or contact the PMT: converge-pm@elixir-europe.org

ANNEX 1: PROJECT GANTT CHART

Description	Lead	M	M	M	M	M	M	M	M	M	M	M	M	M	M
		03	06	09	12	15	18	21	24	27	30	33	36	39	42
WP1 Expert network	UU														
T1.1 Network of data managers and scientific best practice	UU														
T1.2 Models for brokering data to ELIXIR Deposition Databases	EMBL-EBI														
T1.3 Business model	CNR														
T1.4 Sustainable and scalable operating model for harmonised data management in European projects	UOCHB														
WP2 Training and Capacity Building	DTL-Projects														

⁶⁹ <https://drive.google.com/open?id=1K66wz0jDS3K6VypdzyV67P9AIMPpKduW>

⁷⁰ <https://f1000research.com/documents/7-1234>

⁷¹ A fully executed copy of the CA has been circulated to all partners

⁷² <https://drive.google.com/file/d/1gLhclTzFumCGuobTsZBPcZKFcPB2m5Qn/view>

T2.1 Identify training needs and solutions in Data Management and Stewardship	UCAM					
T2.2 Develop best practices guidelines and training materials in DMS	DTL-Proje cts					
T2.3 Capacity Building in Data Management and Stewardship	UL					
T2.4 Outreach activities to new ELIXIR Members and Communities	SIB					
WP3 Common Data Management Toolkit	VIB					
T3.1 Establish a Starter Toolkit	UNIMAN					
T3.2 Processes for enriching, maintaining and sustaining the Toolkit strators	UIB					
T3.3 Access portal to Toolkit tailored to stakeholders	DTL-Proje cts					
T3.4 Best Practices and training	UNILU					
WP4 Communications, Industry, International, Impact and Sustainability	ELIXIR Hub					
T4.1 Delivering world-class communications activities, including project website and presence at key conferences and events	ELIXIR Hub					
T4.2 Operating the ELIXIR Innovation and SME Forum and enhancing implementation of national industry engagement efforts	ELIXIR Hub					
T4.3 Engaging potential new Member countries and enhancing international visibility	ELIXIR Hub					
T4.4 Implementing an impact assessment toolkit for demonstrating ELIXIR’s value, nationally and at European level	ELIXIR Hub					
T4.5 Supporting the long-term sustainability of ELIXIR	ELIXIR Hub					

WP5 Demonstrator Projects	INRAE				
T5.1 Typology of projects based on the type of resources needed to implement a Ma-DMP	INRAE				
T5.2 Implementation of pilots data management plans	BSC				
T5.3 Development, implementation and refinement of key performance indicators to monitor the pilots implementation of data management plans	UIB				
T5.4 Capacity building actions based on pilots outcomes	UL				
WP6 Project Management and Scientific Coordination	ELIXIR Hub				
T6.1 Establishment of project management boards	ELIXIR Hub				
T6.2 Project monitoring and support	ELIXIR Hub				
T6.3 Development and implementation of the project data management plan and correlated activities	ELIXIR Hub				
T6.4 Excellence in Management	ELIXIR Hub				
WP7 Federated European Genome-phenome Archives for transnational access of COVID-19 host data	EMBL-EB I				
T7.1 Architecture, interfaces, and compliance to support EGA federated network on COVID-19 host data management	EMBL-EB I				
T7.2 A technical implementation required for a federated EGA Network	CRG				
T7.3 Coordination of metadata standards for phenotype submission and access of COVID-19 data	CSC				

T7.4 Operational support and maturity model for Federated EGA nodes	BSC				
WP8 ELIXIR-CONVERGE European COVID-19 Data Platform	EMBL-EB I				
T8.1 Data management support	EMBL-EB I				
T8.2 Mobilise analysis	EMBL-EB I				
T8.3 Enhance access	EMBL-EB I				
WP9 Mobilisation of SARS-CoV-2 variant surveillance data tracking services and tools	EMBL-EB I				
T9.1 Strengthen central Covid-19 data portal help desk for individual centers and brokers	EMBL-EB I				
T9.2 Coordinate nascent and established national data hubs focusing on brokering services to mobilise data and define and foster common best practices	SIB				
T9.3 SARS-CoV-2 data standards	UKZN				
T9.4 SARS-CoV-2 Analysis	ALU-FR				

The full project GANTT chart and other project planning information can be found in the Project Master File on the CONVERGE Google Drive⁷³.

⁷³

https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1B_sKgO8uwAQEOGY-PRBGo8HbMgSrlKGE-MCrArKdXWo/edit#gid=434949238

Appendix 2: ELIXIR-CONVERGE Project Handbook - live version

The Project Handbook is accessible to all project Partners on the ELIXIR-CONVERGE Google Drive: [ELIXIR-CONVERGE PROJECT HANDBOOK](https://docs.google.com/document/d/190nhuO4Y-I78HKnFdeLJSRZQEGHDTnNfDU3P2IKFETI/edit?ts=5ea67aef#)⁷⁴

⁷⁴ ELIXIR-CONVERGE Project Handbook:

<https://docs.google.com/document/d/190nhuO4Y-I78HKnFdeLJSRZQEGHDTnNfDU3P2IKFETI/edit?ts=5ea67aef#>

